

Robert Vincent Breunig

Curriculum vitae

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- Contact Information

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- *Web*:
<https://sites.google.com/view/robertvbreunig/home>
- *Citizenship*:
Australian and U.S.

- Academic Background

- *Education*:
Ph. D. (Economics), University of California Riverside, 1998
 - * Dissertation: Econometrics of Household Survey Sampling
Chair: Aman Ullah
 - * Chancellor's Distinguished FellowshipBachelor of International Studies, School for International Training,
Brattleboro, Vermont, 1987
 - * Undergraduate Thesis:
Rural-Urban Migration in the PhilippinesUniversité Catholique de l'Ouest, Angers, France 1984-1985
- *Research Interests*:
Tax and transfer policy
Inter-generational mobility
Childcare and household labour supply
Regulatory and competition economics
Innovation and Productivity
Intra-household economic behavior and aggregation
Econometrics: complex sampling, non-parametrics
Poverty and Inequality
- *Membership of Professional Societies*:
American Economic Association
Econometric Society
Economic Society of Australia
International Institute of Public Finance

- Positions held

- *Current position*

- Director, Tax and Transfer Policy Institute
 - Chair of Tax Policy and Public Finance
 - and Professor of Economics, Crawford School of Public Policy
 - Australian National University (November 2012 -)

- *Other positions*

- Research Affiliate, IZA–Institute of Labor Economics
 - Research Fellow, RFBerlin
 - Board member, Committee for the Economic Development of Australia (CEDA)

- *Honours*

- Fellow, Australian Academy of Social Science
 - Honorary Professor, University of Melbourne
 - President, Economic Society of Australia (August 2025 -)

- *Previous positions*

- Acting Director, Crawford School of Public Policy
 - Australian National University (July 2015 - December 2016)
 - Professor, Research School of Economics
 - Australian National University (August 2010 - November 2012)
 - Associate Professor, Research School of Economics
 - Australian National University (January 2010 - July 2010)
 - Associate Professor, Research School of Social Sciences
 - Australian National University (January 2008 - December 2009)
 - Associate Professor, School of Economics
 - Australian National University (September 2006 - December 2007)
 - Lecturer (in 2001) and then Senior Lecturer, School of Economics
 - Australian National University (January 2001 - August 2006)
 - Lecturer, Department of Statistics and Econometrics
 - Australian National University (July 1998 - December 2000)

- *Visiting positions*

- Lee Kuan Yew School of Public Policy, National University of Singapore–
 - Distinguished Academic Visitor (April 2019)
 - Harris School of Public Policy, University of Chicago
 - (October–November 2013)
 - Institute for Research on Poverty, University of Wisconsin
 - (November–December 2012; October 2015; September 2025)
 - Centre for Studies in Social Sciences, Calcutta
 - (January–February, 2012)
 - Faculté des Sciences Économiques, Université de Rennes I
 - (2003 - today)
 - Department of Economics, University of Wisconsin
 - (April - May 2002 and January 2003)
 - School of Mathematics, University of Southampton
 - (May - June 2002)

- Books

- (1) Fabian, M. and R. Breunig (2018), *Hybrid Public Policy Innovations: Contemporary Policy Beyond Ideology*. New York, NY: Routledge

- Refereed journal publications

- (2) Sobeck, K. and R. Breunig (2026) “Does decreasing the generosity of payments to single parents have employment and earnings effects? Evidence from Australian administrative data” *Economic Record*, forthcoming.
- (3) Sobeck, K. and R. Breunig (2026) “Retirement savings incentives for low and middle income individuals: does government funded matching change behaviour?” *Economic Record*, forthcoming.
- (4) Breunig, R., Cheng, W., Montenovolo, L., Lee, K.H., Weinberg, B. and Y. Zhang (2026) “Cross-Country Analysis of Labor Markets during the COVID-19 Pandemic” *ILR Review*, forthcoming.
- (5) Ranjan, M. and R. Breunig (2026) “Individualized disability support schemes and their impact on autism diagnoses” *Journal of Health Economics*, Volume 105, 103100. Available at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhealeco.2025.103100>
- (6) Majeed, O., J. Hambur and R. Breunig (2025) “Does Monetary Policy Impact Innovation? Evidence from Australian Administrative Data” *Journal of Macroeconomics*, Volume 86, 103706. Available at <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0164070425000424>. Reserve Bank of Australia Research Discussion Paper RDP 2024-01. <https://www.rba.gov.au/publications/rdp/2024/pdf/rdp2024-01.pdf>
- (7) Breunig, R., N. Deutscher and S. Hamilton (2024) “Rounded Up: Using Round Numbers to Identify Tax Evasion” *Journal of Public Economics*, Volume 238, 105195. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpubeco.2024.105195>
- (8) Carter, A. and R. Breunig (2024) “Tax bunching of very high earners: Evidence from Australia’s Division 293 tax” *Economic Record*, Volume 100, Issue 330, pp. 343-372. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1475-4932.12813>
- (9) Vanek, S. and R. Breunig (2024) “The Biosecurity Protection Levy: Principles for design”. *Farm Policy Journal*, Volume 21, Number 2, pp. 22-28.
- (10) Orzechowska-Fischer, E., E. Rose and R. Breunig (2024) “The Dual Risks of Digital Exclusion and Unaffordability of Telecommunications in Lower-Income Australian Households”. *Australian Economic Review*, Volume 57, Issue 4, pp. 319-350. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8462.12569>.
- (11) Bayly, N., R. Breunig and C. Wokker (2024) “Female Board Representation and Corporate Performance: A Review and New Estimates for Australia” *Economic Record*, Volume 100, Issue 330, pp. 386-417. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1475-4932.12795>

- (12) Johnson, S., R. Breunig, M. Olivo-Villabrille and A. Zaresani (2023), “Individuals’ Responsiveness to Marginal Tax Rates: Evidence from Bunching in the Australian Personal Income Tax System” *Labour Economics*, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.labeco.2023.102461>.
- (13) Zhang, J. and R. Breunig (2023), “Gender Norms and Domestic Abuse: Evidence from Australia” *Journal of Population Economics*, Volume 36, pp. 2925-2965. Available at: [Link to paper](#)
Paper awarded Kuznets Prize
- (14) Lancsar, E., E. Huynh, J. Swait, R. Breunig, C. Mitton, M. Kirk and C. Donaldson (2023), “Preparing for future pandemics: a multi-national comparison of health and economic trade-offs” *Health Economics*, Volume 32, Issue 7, pp. 1434-1452. Available at <https://doi.org/10.1002/hec.4673>.
- (15) Fabian, M., R. Breunig and J. De Neve (2023), “Explaining the Return of Racial Voting: Economic Anxiety, Psychological Wellbeing, and Identity” *European Journal of Social Psychology*, Volume 53, Issue 1, pp. 147–166. Available at <https://doi.org/10.1002/ejsp.2894>
- (16) Breunig, R. and T. Sainsbury (2023), “Too much of a good thing? Australian cash transfer replacement rates during the pandemic” *Australian Economic Review*, Volume 56, Issue 1, pp. 70–90.
- (17) Majeed, O. and R. Breunig (2022), “Determinants of Innovation Novelty: Evidence from Australian administrative data” *Innovation and New Technology*, Volume 32, Number 8, pp. 1249–1273. Available at <https://doi.org/10.1080/10438599.2022.2132239>
- (18) Hathorne, C. and R. Breunig (2022), “Occupational Mobility in the ALife data: how reliable are occupational patterns from administrative Australian tax records?” *Economic Papers*, Volume 41, Issue 4, pp. 297–324. Available at <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/1759-3441.12369>.
- (19) Boucher, A., R. Breunig and C. Karmel (2022), “A preliminary literature review on the effect of immigration upon Australian domestic employment and wages” *Australian Economic Review*, Volume 55, Number 2, pp. 263-272.
- (20) Hasan, S., S. Shakur and R. Breunig (2021) “Exchange rates and expenditure of households with foreign-born members: evidence from Australia” *Journal of Economic Behavior and Organization*, Volume 188, pp. 977-997.
- (21) Hasan, S. and R. Breunig (2021) “Article length and citation outcomes” *Scientometrics*, Volume 126, Number 9, pp. 7583-7608.
- (22) Agarwal, A., S. Arfin, R. Breunig, S. Weldeegzie and T. Zhang (2021), “Nationalism and Economic Openness: The cross-country evidence” *Asia Pacific Policy Studies*, Volume 8, Number 3, pp. 420-434.
- (23) Van Kints, M. and R. Breunig (2021), “Inflation Variability across Australian Households: Implications for Inequality and Indexation policy” *Economic Record*, Volume 97, Number 316, pp. 1-23.

- (24) Sainsbury, T. and R. Breunig (2020), "Tax Planning in Australia's Income Tax System" *Agenda: A Journal of Policy Analysis and Reform*, Volume 27, Number 1, pp. 59-83.
- (25) Sainsbury, T. and R. Breunig (2020), "The urgent need for Tax Reform in Australia in the COVID-19 World" *Australian Journal of Labour Economics*, Volume 23, Number 2, pp. 79-97.
- (26) Bakhtiari, S., R. Breunig, E. Magnani and J. Zhang (2020), "Financial Constraints and Small and Medium Enterprises: A Review" *Economic Record*, Volume 96, Number 315, pp. 506-523.
- (27) Breunig, R., D. Hourani, S. Bakhtiari and E. Magnani (2020), "Do financial constraints affect the composition of workers in a firm?" *Australian Journal of Labour Economics*, Volume 23, Number 1, pp. 79-97.
- (28) Freestone, O. and R. Breunig (2020), "Risk aversion and the Elasticity of Intertemporal Substitution among Australian households", *Economic Record*, Volume 96, Number 313, pp. 121-139.
- (29) Breunig, R. and O. McCarthy (2020), "Household Telecommunications Expenditure in Australia" *Telecommunications Policy*, Volume 44, Issue 1, Article 101837.
- (30) Breunig, R. and O. Majeed (2020), "Inequality, Poverty and Economic Growth", *International Economics*, Volume 161, May, pp. 83-99. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.inteco.2019.11.005>.
- (31) Biddle, N., R. Breunig, F. Markham and C. Wokker (2019), "Introducing the longitudinal MADIP and its role in understanding income dynamics in Australia", *Australian Economic Review*, Volume 52, Issue 4, pp. 476-495.
- (32) Breunig, R. S. Hasan and K. Whiteoak (2019), "Value of playgrounds relative to green spaces: Matching evidence from property prices in Australia" *Landscape and Urban Planning*, Volume 190, Article 103608.
- (33) Carter, A. and R. Breunig (2019), "Do earned income tax credits for older workers prolong labor market participation and boost earned income? Evidence from Australia's Mature Age Worker Tax Offset" *Economic Record*, Volume 95, Number 309, pp. 220-226.
- (34) Fabian, M. and R. Breunig (2019), "Long work-hours and job satisfaction: do over-workers get trapped in bad jobs?" *Social Science Quarterly*, Volume 100, Number 5, pp. 1932-1956.
- (35) Breunig, R., S. Hasan and B. Hunter (2019) "Financial Stress and Indigenous Australians." *Economic Record*, Volume 95, Number 308, pp. 34-57.
- (36) van Dijk, A., V. Herrington, H., N. Crofts, R. Breunig, S. Burris, H. Sullivan, S. Sherman and N. Thomson (2019) "Redrawing the Thin Blue Line – Recognizing and Enhancing Joined up Solutions at the Intersection of Law Enforcement and Public Health" *Lancet*, Volume 393, Issue 10168, pp. 287-294. First published online: [https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lancet/article/PIIS0140-6736\(18\)32839-3/fulltext?rss=yes](https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lancet/article/PIIS0140-6736(18)32839-3/fulltext?rss=yes).

- (37) Breunig, R. and S. Bakhtiari (2018), "The Role of Spillovers in Research and Development Expenditure in Australian Industries" *Economics of Innovation and New Technology*, Volume 27, Number 1, pp. 14-38. First published online 21 February 2017, DOI: 10.1080/10438599.2017.1290898.
- (38) Deutscher, N. and R. Breunig (2018) "Baby Bonuses: natural experiments in cash transfers, birth timing and child outcomes" *Economic Record*, Volume 94, Issue 304, pp. 1-24.
- (39) Breunig, R., N. Deutscher and H. T. To (2017), "The relationship between immigration to Australia and the labour market outcomes of Australian-born workers" *Economic Record*, Volume 93, Number 301, pp. 255-276. First published online 10 March 2017, DOI: 10.1111/1475-4932.12328.
- (40) X. Gong and R. Breunig (2017), "Child Care Assistance: Are subsidies or tax credits better?" *Fiscal Studies*, Volume 38, Number 1, pp. 7-48. First published online 23 February 2017, DOI: DOI: 10.1111/1475-5890.12085.
- (41) Bakhtiari, S. and R. Breunig (2017) "New outsourcing, demand uncertainty and labor usage" *Review of Industrial Organization*, Volume 50, Issue 1, pp. 69-90.
- (42) Alexander, B. and R. Breunig (2016), "A Monte Carlo Study of Bias in Panel Probit Models", *Journal of Statistical Computation and Simulation*, Volume 86, Number 1, pp. 74-90. First published online 24 December 2014, DOI: 10.1080/00949655.2014.994516.
- (43) Barbalet, F., J. Greenville, W. Crook, P. Gratton and R. Breunig (2015), "Exploring the links between bilateral and regional trade agreements and merchandise trade" *Asia and the Pacific Policy Studies*, Volume 2, Number 3, pp. 467-484. First published online 17 August 2015, DOI: 10.1002/app5.101.
- (44) Breunig, R., X. Gong and G. Leslie (2015), "The dynamics of satisfaction with working hours in Australia: the usefulness of panel data in evaluating the case for policy intervention" *Asia and the Pacific Policy Studies*, Volume 2, Number 1, pp. 130-154. First published online 19 December 2014, DOI: 10.1002/app5.64.
- (45) Breunig, R. and T. C. Chia (2015), "Sovereign Ratings and Oil-Producing Countries: Have Sovereign Ratings Run Ahead of Fundamentals?" *International Review of Finance*, Volume 15, Number 1, pp. 113-138. First published online 22 July 2014, DOI: 10.1111/irfi.12036.
- (46) X. Gong and R. Breunig (2014), "Channels of labour supply responses of lone parents to changed work incentives" *Oxford Economic Papers*, Volume 66, Number 4, pp. 891-915.
- (47) Breunig, R., B. Garrett-Rumba, Y. Rocaboy and M. Jardin (2014), "Wage dispersion and team performance: a theoretical model and evidence from baseball" *Applied Economics*, Volume 46, Issue 3, pp. 271-281.
- (48) Breunig, R, X. Gong and D. Trott (2014), "The new National Quality Framework: quantifying some of the effects on labour supply, child

care demand and household finances for two-parent households” *Economic Record*, Volume 90, Number 288, pp. 1-16.

Paper awarded *Economic Record* best paper prize

- (49) R. Breunig, S. Hasan and M. Salehin (2013), “The immigrant wage gap and assimilation in Australia: does unobserved heterogeneity matter?” *Economic Record*, Volume 89, Number 287, pp. 490-507.
- (50) Breunig, R. and S. Bakhtiari (2013), “Outsourcing and innovation: An empirical exploration of the dynamic relationship” *BE Journal of Economic Analysis and Policy*, Volume 13, Number 1 (April), pp. 395-418.
- (51) Breunig, R. and S. Rospabe (2013), “The male-female wage gap in France: differences across the wage distribution” *Australian Journal of Labour Economics*, Volume 16, Number 1, pp. 155-199.
- (52) Breunig, R., F. Menezes and K. Tan (2012), “An Empirical Investigation of the Mergers Decision Process in Australia” *Economic Record*, Volume 88, Number 283, pp. 459–475.
- (53) Breunig, R., X. Gong, and A. King (2012), “Partnered women’s labour supply and child care costs in Australia: measurement error and the child care price” *Economic Record*, Volume 88, Special Issue, pp. 51-69.
Paper awarded *Economic Record* best paper prize
- (54) Breunig, R. and R. McKibbin (2012), “Income pooling between Australian young adults and their parents” *Labour: Review of Labour Economics and Industrial Relations*, Volume 26, Number 2, pp. 235-265.
- (55) Breunig, R. and F. Menezes (2012), “Testing Regulatory Consistency” *Contemporary Economic Policy*, Volume 30, Issue 1, pp. 60-74. Available on-line at <http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/j.1465-7287.2010.00249.x/full>
- (56) Breunig, R. (2011), “Should single-equation dynamic gasoline demand models include moving average terms?” *Journal of Transportation Research, Part D*, Volume 16, Issue 6, pp. 474-477.
- (57) Breunig, R. and R. McKibbin (2011), “The Effect of Survey Design on Household Reporting of Financial Difficulty” *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society, Series A*, Volume 174, part 4, pp. 991-1005. Available on-line at <http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/j.1467-985X.2011.00696.x/full>
- (58) Breunig, R., X. Gong, J. Mercante, A. Weiss, and C. Yamauchi (2011), “Child Care Availability, Quality and Affordability: Are Local Problems Related to Labour Supply?” *Economic Record*, Volume 87, Number 276, March, pp. 109-124.
- (59) Breunig, R. and J. Mercante (2010), “The accuracy of predicted wages of the non-employed and implications for policy simulations from structural labour supply models.” *Economic Record*, Volume 86, Number 272, March, pp. 49-70.

- (60) Baron, J., R. Breunig, D. Cobb-Clark, T. Gørgens and A. Sartbayeva (2009), "Does the Effect of Incentive Payments on Survey Response Rates Differ by Income Support History?" *Journal of Official Statistics*, Volume 25, Number 4, pp. 483-507.
- (61) Breunig, R., and C. Gisz (2009), "An Exploration of Australian Petrol Demand: Lagged Adjustment, Unobservable Habits, Irreversibility and Some Updated Estimates." *Economic Record*, Volume 85, Number 268, pp. 73-91.
- (62) Breunig, R. and F. Menezes (2008), "Empirical Approaches for Identifying Maverick Firms: An Application to Mortgage Providers in Australia." *Journal of Competition Law and Economics*, Volume 4, Number 3 (September), pp. 811-836.
- (63) Breunig, R., D. Cobb-Clark and X. Gong (2008), "Improving the Modeling of Couples' Labour Supply." *Economic Record*, Volume 84, Number 267, pp. 466-485.
- (64) Breunig, R. and Y. Rocaboy (2008), "Per-capita public expenditures and population size: a non-parametric analysis using French data." *Public Choice*, Volume 136, Number 3, pp. 429-445.
- (65) Breunig, R. (2008), "Nonparametric Density Estimation for Stratified Samples." *Statistics and Probability Letters*, Volume 78, pp. 2194-2200.
- (66) Breunig, R. and M. Wong (2008), "A Richer Understanding of Australia's Productivity Performance in the 1990s: Improved Estimates Based Upon Firm-level Panel Data." *Economic Record*, Volume 84, Number 265, pp. 157-176.
- (67) Breunig, R. and M. Wong (2007), "The Role of Firm Dynamics in Australia's Productivity Growth." *Australian Economic Review*, Volume 40, Number 1, pp. 90-96.
- (68) Breunig, R. D. Cobb-Clark, X. Gong and D. Venn (2007), "Disagreement in Partners' Reports of Financial Difficulty." *Review of Economics of the Household*, Volume 5, Number 1, January, pp. 59-82.
- (69) Cobb-Clark, D., C. Ryan and R. Breunig (2006), "A couples-based approach to the problem of workless families." *Economic Record*, Volume 82, Number 259, December, pp. 428-444.
- (70) Breunig, R., S. Stacey, J. Hornby and F. Menezes (2006), "Price Regulation in Australia: How consistent has it been?" *Economic Record*, Volume 82, Number 256, March, pp. 67-76.
- (71) Breunig, R. and D. Cobb-Clark, (2006), "Understanding the Factors Associated with Financial Stress in Australian Households" *Australian Social Policy 2005*, pp 13-64.
- (72) Breunig, R. and I. Dasgupta (2005), "Do Intra-household Effects Generate the Food Stamp Cash-Out Puzzle?," *American Journal of Agricultural Economics*, Volume 87, Number 3, pp. 552-568.
- (73) Breunig, R. and A. Stegman, (2005), "Testing for Regime Switching in Singaporean Business Cycles," *Singapore Economic Review*, Volume 50, Number 1, pp. 25-34.

- (74) Breunig, R. and A. Pagan, (2004), “Do Markov-Switching Models Capture Non-linearities in the Data? Tests Using Non-parametric Methods,” *Mathematics and Computers in Simulation*, Volume 64, pp. 401-407.
- (75) Breunig, R., S. Najarian, and A. Pagan (2003), “Specification Testing of Markov-Switching Models,” *Oxford Bulletin of Economics and Statistics*, Volume 65, December, pp. 703-725.
- (76) Breunig, R. and I. Dasgupta, (2003), “Are People Ashamed of Paying with Food Stamps?” *Journal of Agricultural Economics*, Volume 54, Number 2, pp. 203-225.
- (77) Breunig, R., D. Cobb-Clark, Y. Dunlop, and M. Terrill, (2003), “Assisting the Long-term Unemployed: Results from a Randomized Trial,” *Economic Record*, Volume 79, Number 244, pp. 84-102.
- (78) Breunig, R. and I. Dasgupta, (2002), “A Theoretical and Empirical Evaluation of the Functional Forms Used to Estimate the Food Expenditure Equation of Food Stamp Recipients: Comment,” *American Journal of Agricultural Economics*, Volume 84, Number 4, November, pp. 1156-1160.
- (79) Breunig, R., (2002), “Bias correction for inequality measures: an application to China and Kenya,” *Applied Economics Letters*, Number 9, pp. 783-786.
- (80) Breunig, R., (2001), “Density estimation for clustered data,” *Econometric Reviews*, Volume 20, Number 3, pp. 353-367.
- (81) Breunig, R., (2001), “An Almost Unbiased Estimator of the Coefficient of Variation,” *Economics Letters*, Volume 70, Number 1, pp. 15-19.
- (82) Lieberman, O., A. Ullah and R. Breunig, (1997), “On the Bias of the Standard Errors of the LS Residual and the Regression Coefficients Under Normal and Non-Normal Errors,” *Econometric Theory, Problems and Solutions*, Volume 13, December, pp. 896-7.
- (83) Ullah, A. and R. Breunig, (1996), “On the Bias of the Standard Errors of the LS Residual and the Regression Coefficients Under Normal and Non-Normal Errors,” *Econometric Theory, Problems and Solutions*, Volume 12, December, pp. 868.
- Refereed book chapters and monographs
- (84) Breunig, R., L. Jeffrey, G. Fahey and A. Norton (2026), “Child-care, schools and higher education”. *The First Albanese Government: Governing in an Age of Disruption and Division, 2022-2025*, edited by Grattan, M., J. Halligan and J. Hawkins. Chapter 14. Sydney, Australia: New South Publishing.
- (85) Podger, A., R. Breunig and J. Piggott (2023), “Retirement incomes: Increasing Inequity, Not Costs, across Generations is the Intergenerational Problem” in *More Than Fiscal: The Intergenerational Report, Sustainability and Public Policy in Australia*, edited by Podger, A., J. Hall and M. Woods. Chapter 5, pages 77–97. Canberra, Australia: ANU Press.

- (86) Breunig, R. and D. Hutchinson (2008), “Small sample corrections for inequality indices” in *New Econometric Modeling Research*, edited by W. Toggins. Chapter 2, pages 61-83. Hauppauge, NY: Nova Science Publishers, Inc.
- (87) Breunig, R. and M-H. Wong (2005), “Estimation of total factor productivity” in *Quantitative Tools for Microeconomic Policy Analysis*, Canberra: Productivity Commission, pp. 195-214.
- (88) Breunig, R., I. Dasgupta, C. Gundersen, and P. Pattanaik (2001), “Explaining the Food Stamp Cash-out Puzzle.” Washington DC: United States Department of Agriculture, Economic Research Service, Food Assistance and Nutrition Report Number 12. 30 pages.
- (89) Ullah, A. and R. Breunig (1998), “Econometric Analysis in Complex Surveys,” in Giles, D. and A. Ullah, eds, *Handbook of Applied Economic Statistics*, New York: Marcel Dekker, pp. 325-364.
- (90) Russell, R., R. Breunig and C. Chiu, (1998), “Aggregation and Econometric Analysis of Demand and Supply,” in Giles, D. and A. Ullah, eds, *Handbook of Applied Economic Statistics*, New York: Marcel Dekker, pp. 177-236.

- Other notable publications

- (91) Breunig, R., T. Rose and D. Parham (2025), *Asian Productivity Organization (APO) Productivity Readiness 2025*. Asian Productivity Organization. Available at <https://www.apo-tokyo.org/publications/apo-productivity-readiness-2025/>
- (92) Breunig, R., A. Domazet, C. Lim and O. Majeed (2025), “Asymmetries and habit formation in price elasticities in the Australian aviation sector” Treasury Working Paper. Available at <https://treasury.gov.au/publication/p2025-717396>.
- (93) Majeed, O., R. Breunig and A. Domazet (2024), “How competition impacts prices: The Australian aviation sector” Treasury Working Paper. Available at <https://treasury.gov.au/publication/p2024-553588>.
- (94) Sobeck, K., R. Breunig and A. Evans (2022), “Corporate income taxation in Australia: Theory, current practice and future policy directions” Tax and Transfer Policy Institute (TTPI) Policy Report No. 01-2022, Canberra, Australia.
- (95) Parham, D. and R. Breunig (2021), *Asian Productivity Organization (APO) Productivity Readiness 2020*. Asian Productivity Organization. Available at <https://www.apo-tokyo.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/APO-Productivity-Readiness-2020.pdf>
- (96) Podger, A. and R. Breunig (2021), “Completing Australia’s Retirement Income System”. Tax and Transfer Policy Institute (TTPI), Canberra, Australia. Available at https://taxpolicy.crawford.anu.edu.au/sites/default/files/uploads/taxstudies_crawford_anu_edu_au/2021-08/retirement_incomes_report_podger_breunig_2021.pdf

- (97) Biddle, N., R. Breunig and D. Marasinghe (2021), “Attitudes towards and experiences of retirement and social security income during the COVID-recession and initial recovery”. ANU Centre for Social Research and Methods working paper. 4 May 2021. Available at https://csrcm.cass.anu.edu.au/sites/default/files/docs/2021/5/Retirement_income.pdf
- (98) Varela, P., R. Breunig and K. Sobeck (2020), “The Taxation of Savings in Australia: Theory, current practice and future directions”. Tax and Transfer Policy Institute (TTPI) Policy Report No. 01-2020, Canberra, Australia.
- (99) Wokker, C., A. Wiskich and R. Breunig (2020), “Resource Rents, Political Rights and Civil Liberties.” Centre for Applied Macroeconomic Analysis (CAMA) Working Paper.
- (100) Biddle, N., R. Breunig and F. Markham (2019), “Describing the top of the income distribution in Australia”, Centre for Social Research and Methods (CSRM) Working Paper, No. 4/2019.
- (101) Gong, X., R. Breunig and A. King (2010), “New estimates of the relationship between female labour supply and the cost, availability, and quality of child care” *Economic Roundup*. Issue 1, 2010. Canberra, Australia: Australian Government Printing Service (AGPS). Available at http://archive.treasury.gov.au/documents/1783/HTML/docshell.asp?URL=04_New_Estimates_of_Child_Care.htm
- (102) Breunig, R., D. Cobb-Clark, T. Gørgens, C. Ryan and A. Sartbayeva (2009). “User’s Guide to the Youth in Focus Data, Version 2.0” Youth in Focus Project Discussion Paper Series, No. 1, December, 2009. ISBN 1835-4025. Available at http://cbe.anu.edu.au/media/2367269/yif_user_guide_2.0_10dec2009.pdf.
- (103) Breunig, R., D. Cobb-Clark, T. Gørgens and A. Sartbayeva (2007). “User’s Guide to the Youth in Focus Data, Version 1.0” Youth in Focus Project Discussion Paper Series, No. 1, September, 2007. ISBN 1835-4025. Available at http://cbe.anu.edu.au/media/2367248/yif_dp1_yif_technical_paper_1_19_october_07.pdf.

- Selected Working Papers

- (1) Varela, P., R. Breunig and M. Smith (2025) “Measuring the changing size of intergenerational transfers in the Australian tax and transfer system.” Tax and Transfer Policy Institute Working Paper 7/2025. <https://crawford.anu.edu.au/content-centre/research/measuring-changing-size-intergenerational-transfers-australian-tax-and>
- (2) Win, N., J. Hambur and R. Breunig (2025) “When are investment tax breaks effective.” Tax and Transfer Policy Institute Working Paper 1/2025. <https://crawford.anu.edu.au/ttpi/content-centre/research/when-are-investment-tax-breaks-effective>
Submitted to *National Tax Journal*
- (3) Majeed, O., R. Breunig and A. Domazet (2024) “How Competition impacts prices: The Australian Aviation Sector”. Treasury Working

paper. https://treasury.gov.au/sites/default/files/2024-09/p2024-553588_0.pdf

- (4) Gong, X., B. Freyens and R. Breunig (2024) “Compatibility in personalities and non-cognitive skills, problem gambling and relationship dissolution in Australia”. Submitted to *Review of Economics of the Household*.
- (5) Zaresani, A., M. Olivo-Villabrille and R. Breunig (2024) “Tax Sheltering Cost Among High-Income Taxpayers: Evidence from an Australian Tax Policy Change”. Submitted to *Journal of European Economic Association*. Tax and Transfer Policy Institute Working Paper 3/2024. <https://taxpolicy.crawford.anu.edu.au/publication/ttpti-working-papers/21930/tax-sheltering-cost-among-high-income-taxpayers-evidence>.
- (6) Varela, P. and R. Breunig (2024) “Determinants of the economic outcomes of Australian permanent migrants”. Revise and resubmit at *Economic Record*. Tax and Transfer Policy Institute Working Paper 7/2024. <https://crawford.anu.edu.au/ttpti/content-centre/research/determinants-economic-outcomes-australian-permanent-migrants>
- (7) Breunig, R., D. Hansell and N. Win (2023) “Promotion in the Australian Public Service: Improvements for women and stagnation for cultural and linguistic minorities”. Submitted to *Economic Record*. IZA Working Paper No. 16549. <https://docs.iza.org/dp16549.pdf>
- (8) Sainsbury, T., R. Breunig and T. Watson (2022) “COVID-19 Private Pension Withdrawals and Unemployment Tenures”. IZA Working Paper No. 15399. <https://docs.iza.org/dp15399.pdf>
- (9) Chien, C-H., R. Breunig and A. H. Welsh (2022) “Firm-level dynamics and aggregate productivity: Australian evidence using linked employer-employee data” submitted to *Empirical Economics*
- (10) Breunig, R. and M-H. Wong, (2013), “Firm Dynamics and Aggregate Productivity Growth: A Critical Review of Decomposition Analyses” submitted to *Journal of Productivity Analysis*
- (11) Breunig, R., B. Edwards, S. Hasan and B. Hunter (2015), “Natural disasters and financial stress in agricultural areas”

Full details of working papers and current unpublished work can be accessed at my web page <https://sites.google.com/view/robertvbreunig/home>. Feel free to email me for working paper copies if you cannot find them robert.breunig@anu.edu.au.

- Major Grants

- (1) Australian Research Council Discovery Grant. *Chief Investigator*
Title: *Better childcare policy: parental labour supply and provider responses.*
Co-investigators: C. Labanca and S. Griselda
Amount: \$656,000
Dates: 2026 - 2028
- (2) Australian Research Council Linkage Grant. *Chief Investigator*
Title: *The Use of Nudges as a Local Government Environmental Policy Instrument.*
Co-investigators: M. Sinning, R. Steinhauser, and J. Zhang
Amount: \$136,994
Dates: 2023 - 2025
- (3) Australian Research Council Discovery Grant. *Chief Investigator*
Title: *Problem gambling: effects on families, children and spouses.*
Co-investigators: B. Freyens and X. Gong
Amount: \$215,315
Dates: 2021 - 2023
- (4) Australian Research Council Discovery Grant. *Chief Investigator*
Title: *Small firms' finances: effects on employment, wages and growth.*
Co-investigators: E. Magnani, D. Prentice and S. Bakhtiari
Amount: \$239,000
Dates: 2016 - 2018
- (5) Australian Research Council Linkage Grant. *Chief Investigator*
Title: *Applying Behavioural Insights to the Tax System in Australia.*
Co-investigators: M. Stewart, N. Biddle, M. Sinning, G. Issar, and C. Griffin
Amount: \$217,000
Dates: 2016 - 2018
- (6) Australian Research Council Discovery Grant. *Chief Investigator*
Title: *Taxation, family policy and pension reform in an uncertain economy.*
Co-investigators: P. Apps, A. Booth, R. Rees, and A. van Soest
Amount: \$580,000
Dates: 2010 - 2012
- (7) Australian Research Council Discovery Grant. *Chief Investigator*
Title: *The consistency of price regulation of infrastructure businesses across Australian jurisdictions.*
Co-investigator: F. Menezes
Amount: \$255,000
Dates: 2006 - 2008
- (8) Australian Research Council Linkage Grant. *Chief Investigator*
Title: *Intergenerational transmission of dependence on income support: patterns, causation, and implications for Australian social policy.*
Linkage partner: Department of Family and Community Services.
Amount: \$1,554,600 (\$500,000 from Australian Research Council)

and \$1,054,600 partner contribution from Department of Family and Community Services

Co-investigators: D. Cobb-Clark, T. Gørgens, R. Haveman, R. Wolff, J. Pech and J. Borland

Dates: 2004 - 2008

- (9) Australian Research Council Discovery Grant. *Chief Investigator*
Title: *Literacy and numeracy, schooling, neighborhoods and labour market success.*
Co-investigators: B. Chapman, T. Crossley, and C. Ryan
Amount: \$260,000
Dates: 2003 - 2005
- (10) Australian Research Council Discovery Grant. *Chief Investigator*
Title: *Taxation and the welfare state: implications of current policy directions for saving, fertility, economic growth and inequality.*
Co-investigators: P. Apps and R. Rees
Amount: \$260,000
Dates: 2002 - 2004
- (11) Australian Research Council Small Grant. *Chief Investigator*
Title: *Measurement Error and Panel Data: A Non-parametric approach*
Co-investigator: N. Roy
Amount: \$8,360
Dates: 2000
- (12) Australian National University, Faculties New Starters Grant Scheme. *Chief Investigator*
Title: *Non-parametric regression analysis using complex survey data*
Amount: \$5,000
Dates: 1999
- (13) Australian National University, Faculty of Economics and Commerce Summer Research Grant Scheme. *Chief Investigator*
Title: *Bias correction for inequality measures*
Dates: Summer 1999-2000
- (14) Australian National University, Faculty of Economics and Commerce Summer Research Grant Scheme. *Chief Investigator*
Title: *Non-parametric regression with stratified samples*
Dates: Summer 1998-1999

- Courses Taught

- Undergraduate
 - Econometric Methods (2nd year): S1 2003
 - Econometric Modelling (2nd year): S2 2000; S2 2001; S2 2010–2012
 - Applied Econometric Models (3rd year): S2 1999; S2 2000–2007
 - Industrial Organization (Université de Rennes I): S1 2010
 - Multivariate Statistical Analysis (3rd year): S2 1998
 - Design of Experiments and Surveys (3rd year): S1 1999
- Graduate and Honours
 - Economics for Government: S1 2013–2018; S2 2018-2025
 - Graduate Preparatory Econometrics: W 2021-2023
 - Empirical Public Finance: S2 2019
 - Case Studies in Applied Econometrics: S1 2014–2017
 - Applied Econometric Models (Honours): S2 1999; S2 2000; S2 2001; S2 2002; S2 2003; S2 2004; S2 2006
 - Quantitative Techniques in Regulation and Competition Policy (Masters): S2 2005; S1 2006
 - Case Studies in Applied Econometrics (Ph. D.): S2 1998; S2 1999; S2 2002; S2 2003; S2 2004; S2 2005; S2 2006
 - Economic Models and Introductory Econometrics (Ph. D.): S2 1999; S2 2000; S1 2007; S1 2008
 - Reading Course in Panel Data (Honours): S1 2000; S2 2001

- Student Supervision

* indicates chair

- Ph.D. Students
 - Will Mackey * (current)
 - Phillip Womack * (current)
 - Philip Harber * (current)
 - Jonathan Hambur * (current)
 - Lachlan Vass * (current)
 - Josiah Hickson * (current)
 - Sharon Rosenrauch (current)
 - Sadia Islam * (current)
 - Aaron Mollross * (current)
 - Ben Dolman * (current)
 - David Hansell * (current)
 - Beth Ma * (current)
 - Matthew Smith * (current)
 - Maathu Ranjan * (current)
 - Cecilia Karmel * (current)
 - Kristen Sobeck * (current)
 - Nu Nu Win* (current)
 - Jyoti Rahman* (current)
 - Tristram Sainsbury* (2023)

Matthew Taylor*
Kevin Chadwick (2023)
Jian Ding (2021)
Andrew Carter* (2023)
Sora Lee (2022)
Thomas Abhayaratna* (current)
Shane Johnson* (2023)
Paul Amores* (2024)
Nurina Merdikawati (2022)
Chris Wokker* (2021)
Tong Zhang (2021)
Hang Hoang (2021)
Joseph Chien (2020)
Nicholas Bayly* (2020)
Owen Freestone* (2020)
Sehrish Mohammed Hussein (2019)
Nathan Deutscher* (2019)
Mark Fabian* (2019)
Sanghyeok Lee (2019)
Samuel Weldeegzie* (2017)
Adriyanto Adriyanto (2017)
Mandy Yap (2017)
Syed Hasan* (2014)
Dana Hanna (2014)
Akhmad A. Susanto* (2013)
Davaajargal Luvsannyam (2012)
Mathieu Jardin (2012)
Taya Dumrongrittikul (2011)
Tanuja Doss* (2011)
Michael Palmer (2011)
Huong Le (2010)
Ariane Utomo (2010)
Simon Zheng (2010)
Daniel Suryadama (2010)
Declan Trott* (2010)
Dilaka Lathapipat (2009)
Christine Yeo (2008)
Benoit Freyens (2007)
Nicholas Biddle (2007)
Hiau Joo Kee (2007)
Marcin Pracz (2007)
Jocelyn Finlay (2006)
Sambit Bhattacharyya (2006)
Marn-Heong Wong* (2005)
Alison Stegman (2004)
Lixin Cai (2002)
Akihito Asano (2001)
Robert Ackland (2000)

– Honours Students

Sehrish Mohammed Hussein (2013)
Ruth Tay (2012)
Bronwyn Garrett-Rumba (2011)
Mosfequs Salehin (2011)
Alex Olssen (2010)
Rebecca McKibbin (2007)
Declan Trott (2003)
Katherine Fewell (2002)
Bonny Parkinson (2002)
David Watts (2000)

– Econometric Case Studies
Jared Bullen (2012)
Owen Freestone (2012)
Azadeh Abbasi (2012)
Blair Alexander (2011)
Pamela Katic (2008)
Joseph Mercante (2006)
Nhat Minh Phan Huu (2006)
Michelle Tan (2005)
Thea Hutchinson (2004)
Alison Stegman (2002)
Anurag Sharma (2001)
Taro Takahashi (2001)
Max Tani (2000)
Yu Yu Chen (1999)
Tetsuya Honda (1998)

- University Service

- Member, University’s Socially Responsible Investment Policy working group, (April 2019 - present)
- Director, Tax and Transfer Policy Institute, (January 2018 - present)
- Director of International Development and Partnerships, Crawford School of Public Policy, (January 2017 - December 2020)
- Member of Crawford Gender Equity and Diversity Committee, Crawford School of Public Policy, (January 2016 - December 2020)
- Acting Director, Crawford School of Public Policy, (July 2015 - December 2016)
- Director, International and Development Economics (IDEC) program, Crawford School of Public Policy, (2015)
- ANU Academic staff representative to UniSuper Consultative Committee, (2005 - present)
- Liaison to Coombs Policy Forum and Australian National Institute for Public Policy from Research School of Economics, (2011 - 2012)
- Member, Short-term Economic Research Project (SERP) committee, (2010 - 2012)

- Economics, Commerce, and Government Library Advisory Committee, ECGLAC, (2000 - 2009)
- Social Sciences, Humanities and Law Advisory Committee, SSSLAC, (2003 - 2009)
- Member, College of Arts and Social Sciences Research Committee, (2008 - 2009)
- Chair of interview committee at ASSA meetings for interviews, Economics, 2004, 2006 and 2008
- Convenor, Master's of Economics programs, Australian National University. (2006 - 2007)
- Representative of Faculty of Economics and Commerce, ANU Open Day, (1998 - 2007)
- Representative of Faculty of Economics and Commerce, Enrollment week, (1998 - 2007)
- Search Committee for Lecturer Position, Social Policy Research and Evaluation (SPEAR) Centre (2004)
- Interview Committee for Lecturer Position, School of Economics (2004)
- Search Committee for Lecturer Position, Social Policy Research and Evaluation (SPEAR) Centre (2003)
- Staff Liaison for Econometrics Chair, School of Economics (2003)
- Staff Liaison for Economics Chair, School of Economics (2002)
- Search Committee for Lecturer Position, Research School of Asian and Pacific Studies (2002)

- Referee and Review Activities

- (1) Journal of Population Economics (December 2025)
- (2) Journal of Labor Economics (December 2025)
- (3) Applied Economics (November 2025)
- (4) Journal of Urban Affairs (November 2025)
- (5) Economic Record (August 2025)
- (6) Economic Record (June 2025)
- (7) Journal of Population Economics (May 2025)
- (8) Australian Tax Forum (May 2025)
- (9) Economic Papers (May 2025)
- (10) Journal of Population Economics (February 2025)
- (11) Small Business Economics (January 2025)
- (12) International Tax and Public Finance (November 2024)
- (13) Urban Studies (October 2024)
- (14) Australian Journal of Labour Economics (October 2024)

- (15) Journal of Infrastructure, Policy and Development (JIPD) (September 2024)
- (16) Journal of Public Economics (June, 2024)
- (17) Productivity Commission (June, 2024)
- (18) Reserve Bank of Australia (June, 2024)
- (19) Psychology, Public Policy & Law (May, 2024)
- (20) Managerial Finance (March, 2024)
- (21) Journal of Scholarly Publishing (November, 2023)
- (22) Economic Record (October, 2023)
- (23) National Tax Journal (July, 2023)
- (24) Applied Economics (July, 2023)
- (25) Review of Income and Wealth (May, 2023)
- (26) Applied Economics (January, 2023)
- (27) Landscape and Urban Planning (October, 2022)
- (28) Australian Economic Review (September, 2022)
- (29) Economic Record (August, 2022)
- (30) Economics of Innovation and New Technology (July, 2022)
- (31) Australian Research Council Discovery Grants (July, 2020)
- (32) Empirical Economics (May, 2022)
- (33) LABOUR: Review of Labour Economics and Industrial Relations (March, 2022)
- (34) Economics of Innovation and New Technology (March, 2022)
- (35) Indian Economic Journal (March, 2022)
- (36) Australian Tax Forum (October, 2021)
- (37) Economic Record (October, 2021)
- (38) Journal of Political Economy (September, 2021)
- (39) Economic Record (September, 2021)
- (40) Australian Journal of Agricultural and Resource Economics (July, 2021)
- (41) Financial Innovation (July, 2021)
- (42) eJournal of Tax Research (June, 2021)
- (43) Landscape and Urban Planning (April, 2021)
- (44) Economic Record (October, 2020)
- (45) Journal of Economic Inequality (September, 2020)
- (46) Economic Inquiry (September, 2020)
- (47) Annals of Regional Science (September, 2020)
- (48) Landscape and Urban Planning (July, 2020)
- (49) Australian Research Council Discovery Grants (May, 2020)
- (50) Asian-Pacific Economic Literature (April, 2020)

- (51) Economic Record (October, 2019)
- (52) Economic Record (May, 2019)
- (53) Australian Research Council Early Career Researcher Grants (May, 2019)
- (54) Economic Record (March, 2019)
- (55) Applied Economics (March, 2019)
- (56) Applied Economics (February, 2019)
- (57) Australian Economic Review (January, 2019)
- (58) Economic Record (December, 2018)
- (59) Communications in Statistics–Theory and Methods (September, 2018)
- (60) Economic Record (September, 2018)
- (61) Australian Research Council Linkage Projects (2018)
- (62) Economic Record (July, 2018)
- (63) Australian Tax Forum (July, 2018)
- (64) Australian Journal of Public Administration (June, 2018)
- (65) Metrika (May, 2018)
- (66) Australian Economic Papers (February, 2018)
- (67) Australian Economic Review (February, 2018)
- (68) Economic Record (July, 2017)
- (69) Labour Economics (June, 2017)
- (70) Applied Economics (June, 2017)
- (71) Applied Economic Perspectives & Policy (April, 2017)
- (72) Economic Record (April, 2017)
- (73) Applied Economics (December, 2016)
- (74) Canadian Journal of Economics (October, 2016)
- (75) Empirical Economics (August, 2016)
- (76) Labour Economics (July, 2016)
- (77) Applied Economics (June, 2016)
- (78) American Journal of Agricultural Economics (May, 2016)
- (79) Urban Studies (May, 2016)
- (80) Journal of Statistical Computation and Simulation (April, 2016)
- (81) Productivity Commission (April, 2016)
- (82) Economic Record (February 2016)
- (83) Empirical Economics (November 2015)
- (84) Productivity Commission (August, 2015)
- (85) Economic Record (July 2015)
- (86) Contemporary Economics (July 2015)
- (87) Journal of Statistical Computation and Simulation (May 2015)

- (88) Commonwealth Department of Employment (May 2015)
- (89) Productivity Commission (April, 2015) [3 papers]
- (90) Asia Pacific Policy Studies (April, 2015)
- (91) Journal of Applied Statistics (February, 2015)
- (92) Journal of Banking and Finance (December, 2014)
- (93) Australian Journal of Labour Economics (December, 2014)
- (94) Economics of Energy & Environmental Policy (November, 2014)
- (95) Economics of Energy & Environmental Policy (October, 2014)
- (96) Asian-Pacific Economic Literature (November, 2014)
- (97) Economic Record (October, 2014)
- (98) Australian Economic Review (April, 2014)
- (99) Economic Record (April, 2014)
- (100) Journal of Agricultural and Resource Economics (April, 2014)
- (101) Empirical Economics (December, 2013)
- (102) Energy Journal (December, 2013)
- (103) Applied Economics (December, 2013)
- (104) Journal of Applied Statistics (November, 2013)
- (105) Asian-Pacific Economic Literature (September, 2013)
- (106) Economic Record (August, 2013)
- (107) Urban Studies (July, 2013)
- (108) Review of Economics of the Household (June, 2013)
- (109) Management Research Review (May, 2013)
- (110) Australian Research Council Discovery Grants (May, 2013)
- (111) Journal of Applied Statistics (May, 2013)
- (112) Economic Record (May, 2013)
- (113) Journal of the Asia Pacific Economy (April, 2013)
- (114) Business Performance Management (April, 2013)
- (115) Empirical Economics (February, 2013)
- (116) Social Science and Humanities Research Council (Canada), Reader (February, 2013)
- (117) Journal of International Money and Finance (January, 2013)
- (118) Australian Journal of Labour Economics (September, 2012)
- (119) Economic Record (June, 2012)
- (120) International Journal of Forecasting (February, 2012)
- (121) The Social Science Journal (December, 2011)
- (122) Statistica Sinica (December, 2011)
- (123) Review of Development Economics (November, 2011)
- (124) Economic Record (November, 2011)

- (125) Economic Record (November, 2011)
- (126) Australian Bulletin of Labour (November, 2011)
- (127) Review of Industrial Organization (October, 2011)
- (128) Journal of Applied Statistics (August, 2010)
- (129) Australian Research Council, Early Career Researcher Grant Program (July, 2011)
- (130) Energy Journal (July, 2011)
- (131) Agricultural Science (June, 2011)
- (132) Australian Research Council, Discovery Projects (May, 2011)
- (133) Review of Economics of the Household (February, 2011)
- (134) Revue Economique (January, 2011)
- (135) Review of Economics of the Household (January, 2011)
- (136) SAGE books (January, 2011)
- (137) Social Science and Humanities Research Council (Canada), Reader (December, 2010)
- (138) Economic Record (September, 2010)
- (139) Journal of Applied Statistics (June, 2010)
- (140) Journal of Population Economics (October, 2009)
- (141) Energy Journal (June, 2009)
- (142) Annales d'Economie et de Statistique (June, 2009)
- (143) International Journal of Statistics and Management Systems (June, 2009)
- (144) Review of Income and Wealth (May, 2009)
- (145) Economic Record (May, 2009)
- (146) Economic Analysis and Policy (May, 2009)
- (147) Australian Economic Review (May, 2009)
- (148) Journal of Economics and Statistics (January, 2009)
- (149) Energy Journal (October, 2008)
- (150) Review of Income and Wealth (June, 2008)
- (151) Journal of Applied Statistics (June, 2008)
- (152) Australian Research Council, Reader for International Linkage Grants Program (June, 2008)
- (153) Review of the National Innovation System for Australian Bureau of Statistics (May, 2008)
- (154) Journal of Productivity Analysis (April, 2008)
- (155) Labour (April, 2008)
- (156) Journal of Economic Surveys (April, 2008)
- (157) Australian Journal of Labour Economics (April, 2008)
- (158) Australian Economic Papers (March, 2008)

- (159) Agenda (October, 2007)
- (160) Journal of Population Economics (September, 2007)
- (161) Australian Research Council, Reader for International Linkage Grants Program (July, 2007)
- (162) Economic Record (June, 2007)
- (163) Australian Research Council, Reader for Discovery Grant Program (May, 2007)
- (164) American Journal of Agricultural Economics (March, 2007)
- (165) Economic Record (March, 2007)
- (166) American Journal of Agricultural Economics (August, 2006)
- (167) Journal of Population Economics (March, 2006)
- (168) Methodology of Longitudinal Surveys (March, 2006)
- (169) Economic Record (December, 2005)
- (170) Economic Record (November, 2005)
- (171) American Journal of Agricultural Economics (October, 2005)
- (172) Journal of Applied Econometrics (October, 2005)
- (173) Economic Record (October, 2005)
- (174) Agenda (September, 2005)
- (175) B.E. Journals in Economic Analysis & Policy (July, 2005)
- (176) Economic Record (June, 2005)
- (177) Australian Research Council, Reader for Discovery Grant Program (May, 2005)
- (178) Journal of Business and Economic Statistics (November, 2004)
- (179) Journal of Population Economics (November, 2004)
- (180) Australian Economic Review (November, 2004)
- (181) Journal of Economic Surveys (July, 2004)
- (182) Australian Research Council, Reader for Discovery Grant Program (May, 2004)
- (183) Social Science and Humanities Research Council (Canada), Reader (December, 2003)
- (184) Australian Economic Review (December, 2003)
- (185) Journal of Population Economics (November, 2003)
- (186) Econometrica (August, 2003)
- (187) Agenda (August, 2003)
- (188) Empirical Economics (July, 2003)
- (189) Australian Research Council, Reader for Discovery Grant Program (May, 2003)
- (190) Review of International Economics (May, 2003)
- (191) Economic Record (April, 2003)

- (192) Economic Record (March, 2003)
- (193) Journal of Productivity Analysis (November, 2002)
- (194) Australian Economic Review (November, 2002)
- (195) Economic Record (May, 2002)
- (196) Journal of International Trade and Economic Development (April, 2001)
- (197) Economic Record (June, 2000)
- (198) U.S. Department of Agriculture (June, 2000)
- (199) Econometric Reviews (March, 2000)
- (200) U.S. National Science Foundation (January, 2000)
- (201) Econometric Reviews (December, 1999)
- (202) Econometric Reviews (April, 1999)
- (203) Empirical Economics (November, 1998)
- (204) Journal of Development Economics (September, 1998)
- (205) Empirical Economics (October, 1997)
- (206) Handbook of Applied Economic Statistics (May, 1996)
- (207) Handbook of Applied Economic Statistics (April, 1996)
- (208) Journal of Quantitative Economics (December, 1995)
- (209) Empirical Economics (October, 1995)

- Selected Presentations

- (1) Annual Economic and Social Policy Lecture, University of Wollongong, November, 2025, “Evidence, Equity and Efficiency: How data can shape smarter government”
- (2) 16th Australasian Public Choice Conference, Deakin University, Melbourne, November, 2025 “Building a Skilled and Adaptable Workforce in the Age of AI, Inequality, and Productivity Challenges”
- (3) Policy for People Workshop, Kioloa, November, 2025, “An overview of research on the Australian childcare system”
- (4) Policy for People Workshop, Kioloa, November, 2025, “Compatibility in personalities and non-cognitive skills and relationship dissolution in Australia”
- (5) Economics in the Pub, Young Economists Network, Canberra, October 2025, “Inter-generational issues in tax”
- (6) Australian Shareholders Association, Canberra, October 2025, “Australia’s Intergenerational Shift: Implications for Policy and Investment”
- (7) The Kids Research Institute, Perth, October 2025, “Using Economic Methods to Understand Policy Impacts and Social Gradients in Life Outcomes”
- (8) Economics on the Swan, Economic Society of Australia, Perth, October 2025, “Reflections on the Economic Reform Roundtable and prospects for tax reform”
- (9) Western Australian Treasury, Perth, October, 2025, “Inter-generational equity”
- (10) Australian Treasury, Canberra, July, 2025, “Inter-generational equity”
- (11) Australian Conference of Economists, Sydney, July, 2025, “Special session on fiscal policy”
- (12) Australian Conference of Economists, Sydney, July, 2025, “Tax reform—where are we headed?”
- (13) ABS/RBA Conference on Opening Doors: Data and analytics shedding light on housing challenges, Sydney, June, 2025, “Inter-generational equity”
- (14) The Tax Institute NSW Tax Forum, Sydney, May, 2025, “Tax reform—where are we headed?”
- (15) University of Western Australia, Perth, May, 2025, “Tax Sheltering Cost Among High-Income Taxpayers: Evidence from an Australian Tax Policy Change”.
- (16) Curtin University, Perth, May, 2025, “Individualized disability support schemes and their impact on autism diagnoses”.
- (17) Purdue University, West Lafayette, IN, April, 2025, “Tax Sheltering Cost Among High-Income Taxpayers: Evidence from an Australian Tax Policy Change”.

- (18) Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development, Paris, December, 2024, “Insights from Australian Taxation Data”
- (19) Australian Academy of Social Sciences, 2024 Keith Hancock Lecture, Sydney, October, 2024, “Tax reform: Laying the foundations”
- (20) Université de Rennes I, France, November, 2024, “Tax Sheltering Cost Among High-Income Taxpayers: Evidence from an Australian Tax Policy Change”.
- (21) Centre for Independent Studies, Consilium, Gold Coast, October, 2024, “Priorities for tax reform in Australia”
- (22) Australian Treasury, October, 2024, “Tax Bunching of very high earners. Evidence from Australia’s Division 293 tax”
- (23) 80th Annual Congress of the International Institute of Public Finance, Prague University of Business and Economics, August, 2024, “Tax Sheltering Cost Among High-Income Taxpayers: Evidence from an Australian Tax Policy Change”
- (24) Malaysia Productivity Corporation, Ministry of Investment Trade and Industry, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, June, 2024, “Addressing Malaysia’s Productivity Challenges”
- (25) Ministerial Advisory Council on Skilled Migration (MACSM), Department of Home Affairs, Canberra, Australia, May, 2024, “What does the data tell us about migrant success”
- (26) Universities Australia Solution Summit 2024, Canberra, Australia, March, 2024, “Australia’s Productivity Challenges”
- (27) Public Policy Network Conference 2024, UNSW, Sydney, Australia, February, 2024, “Heterogeneous effects of payments to single mothers: Evidence from Australia”
- (28) Asian and Australasian Society of Labor Economics Conference, National University of Taiwan, December, 2023, “Female Board Representation and Corporate Performance: A Review and New Estimates for Australia”.
- (29) Asian and Australasian Society of Labor Economics Conference, National University of Taiwan, December, 2023, “Does decreasing the generosity of payments to single parents have employment and earnings effects? Evidence from Australian administrative data”.
- (30) “Promotion and separation in the Australian Public Service: The large effect of ethnicity”. Presented over 40 times to government agencies in Canberra and state capitols (list available upon request).
- (31) Victorian Department of Treasury and Finance, November 2023, “Review of the robustness of the Commonwealth Grants Commission’s Justice assessment data and method”.
- (32) National Tax Association’s Annual Conference on Taxation, November 2023, “Hundreds and Thousands: Bunching at Positive, Salient Tax Balances and the Cost of Reducing Tax Liabilities”.
- (33) Labour Econometrics Workshop, University of Technology Sydney, August 2023, “Cost of income sheltering behaviours and elasticity of taxable income for high income individuals”.

- (34) Labour Econometrics Workshop, University of Technology Sydney, August 2023, “Does decreasing the generosity of payments to single parents have employment and earnings effects? Evidence from Australian administrative data”.
- (35) Australian Workshop on Public Finance, Canberra, August 2023, “Cost of income sheltering behaviours and elasticity of taxable income for high income individuals”.
- (36) Australian Workshop on Public Finance, Canberra, August 2023, “Do business tax breaks work? Evidence from Australia”.
- (37) Economic Society of Australia, Policy Forum: Fiscal Policy for COVID-19, May 2023, “Too much of a good thing? Australian Cash Transfer Replacement Rates During the Pandemic”.
- (38) Victoria Department of Treasury and Finance, May 2023, “Determinants of innovation novelty: Evidence from Australia”.
- (39) Department of Employment, Canberra, March, 2023, “COVID-19 private pension withdrawals and unemployment tenures”.
- (40) Université de Rennes I, France, January, 2023, “Payments to single mothers in Australia: employment effects of benefit reduction and increased work requirements”.
- (41) University of Indiana, December, 2022, “COVID-19 private pension withdrawals and unemployment tenures”.
- (42) Asian and Australasian Society of Labor Economics Conference, University of Tokyo, December, 2022, “Resource cost of income sheltering behaviours and elasticity of taxable income”.
- (43) Asian and Australasian Society of Labor Economics Conference, University of Tokyo, December, 2022, “COVID-19 private pension withdrawals and unemployment tenures”.
- (44) Asian and Australasian Society of Labor Economics Conference, University of Tokyo, December, 2022, “Mental health and duration off income support”.
- (45) University of Adelaide, November, 2022, “COVID-19 private pension withdrawals and unemployment tenures”.
- (46) Australian Bureau of Statistics, Canberra, October, 2022, “COVID-19 private pension withdrawals and unemployment tenures”.
- (47) University of Melbourne, October, 2022, “COVID-19 private pension withdrawals and unemployment tenures”.
- (48) University of Sydney, September, 2022, “COVID-19 private pension withdrawals and unemployment tenures”.
- (49) Reserve Bank of Australia, Sydney, September, 2022, “COVID-19 private pension withdrawals and unemployment tenures”.
- (50) Monash University, Melbourne, August, 2022, “COVID-19 private pension withdrawals and unemployment tenures”.
- (51) Productivity Commission, Canberra, May 2023, “Determinants of innovation novelty: Evidence from Australia”.

- (52) Université de Rennes I, France, April, 2022, “COVID-19 private pension withdrawals and unemployment tenures”.
- (53) “Australia’s future: tax, productivity and federation”. TTPI Workshop, Crawford School of Public Policy, Australian National University, September 2021.
- (54) Panelist, “Regulation and Taxation of MNEs in the Digital Economy”, Crawford Leadership Forum, Crawford School of Public Policy, Australian National University, September 2021.
- (55) Economics Department, Crawford School of Public Policy, Australian National University, Canberra, June 2021 “Gender Norms and Domestic Abuse: Evidence from Australia”
- (56) Department of Social Services, Canberra, April 2021 “Gender Norms and Domestic Abuse: Evidence from Australia”
- (57) UNSW Business School, Sydney, March, 2021, “The incidence of the superannuation guarantee”
- (58) Property Gurus Let’s Chat Forum, Melbourne, March, 2021, “Land tax and stamp duty: evaluating the proposal of NSW Treasury”
- (59) The Tax Summit, Project Reform, Sydney, November, 2020, “Reform Issues and Opportunities: The Case for Reform”
- (60) The Tax Summit, Project Reform, Sydney, November, 2020, “Reform Issues and Opportunities: Streamlining the Tax System for Individuals”
- (61) Productivity Commission, Canberra, November, 2020, “How to improve the taxation of savings in Australia”
- (62) Australian Treasury, Canberra, September, 2020, “How to improve the taxation of savings in Australia”
- (63) Parliamentary Library, Canberra, September, 2020, “Should Australia have a Digital Services Tax (DST)?”
- (64) Tax and Transfer Policy Institute, National Covid-19 Tax Summit, August, 2020, “Where to from here with tax reform?”
- (65) Tax and Transfer Policy Institute Webinar, April, 2020, “Taxes and transfers in the time of COVID-19: A brownbag with Robert Breunig and Steven Hamilton”
- (66) Victoria Treasury, Melbourne, March, 2020, “How do taxpayers respond to the tax system?”
- (67) Asian and Australasian Society of Labour Economics (AASLE), Singapore, December 2019, “Costs of gaming the Australian tax system”
- (68) TTPI workshop on the savings of taxation, Sydney, December 2019, “Key insights from the TTPI report on the taxation of savings”
- (69) Economics Department, Massey University, Palmerston North, New Zealand, November, 2019, “Taxpayer responsiveness to marginal tax rates: Bunching evidence from the Australian personal income tax system”
- (70) Massey University Economics Workshop, Palmerston North, New Zealand, November, 2019, “Grant writing and attracting funding”

- (71) Department of Employment, Canberra, November, 2019, “Hours mismatch and worker satisfaction”
- (72) Commonwealth Department of Infrastructure, Canberra, November, 2019, “Economic modelling of regional issues”
- (73) Economics Department, Ho Chi Minh Economics University, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam, October, 2019, “The Australian Tax System: An overview and priorities for reform”
- (74) Economics Department, National Economics University, Hanoi, Vietnam, October, 2019, “The Australian Tax System: An overview and priorities for reform”
- (75) Central Institute for Economic Management, Hanoi, Vietnam, October, 2019, “The Australian Tax System: An overview and priorities for reform”
- (76) Australian Taxation Office, Canberra, October, 2019, “Hybrid Public Policy”
- (77) Parliamentary Budget Office, Canberra, September, 2019, “Women’s labour supply and child care subsidies”
- (78) Prime Minister and Cabinet, Canberra, October 2019. “The effects of immigration on the labour market outcomes of Australians”
- (79) Parliamentary Budget Office, Canberra, October 2019. “The effects of immigration on the labour market outcomes of Australians”
- (80) Australian Taxation Office, Canberra, September, 2019, “Women’s labour supply and child care subsidies”
- (81) Korea, China and Australia Tax Policy Symposium, Seoul, Korea, August 2019, “Bunching and the elasticity of taxable income: evidence from Australia”
- (82) Social Policy Division, Prime Minister and Cabinet, Canberra, August 2019, “Economics and Social Policy”
- (83) Parliamentary Budget Office, Canberra, July 2019. “The effect on employment and hours of reforms to Parenting Payment Single and Family Tax Benefits”
- (84) Commonwealth Department of Industry, Canberra, June 2019, “Hybrid Public Policy for the people!”
- (85) 2019 Barossa Convention, The Tax Institute, Adelaide, South Australia, May 2019, “Tax Policy Keynote Presentation: Tax and the Economy—Policy and Performance.”
- (86) Commonwealth Department of Industry, Canberra, April 2019, “The effects of immigration on employment and wages of incumbent Australians.”
- (87) Lee Kuan Yew School of Public Policy, National University of Singapore, April 2019, “Inequality, Poverty and Economic Growth”
- (88) Asian and Australasian Society of Labour Economics (AASLE), Seoul, South Korea, December 2018, “Playgrounds and property prices”
- (89) Australian Taxation Office, Canberra, December 2018, “The effect of the Baby Bonus on NAPLAN scores.”

- (90) Hefei University of Technology, Hefei, China, November 2018, “Inequality, Poverty and Economic Growth”
- (91) Central University of Finance and Economics, Beijing, China, November 2018, “Inequality, Poverty and Economic Growth”
- (92) Jiangxi Agricultural University, Jiangxi, China, November 2018, “Inequality, Poverty and Economic Growth”
- (93) Australian Taxation Office, Canberra, October 2018, “Bunching and the elasticity of taxable income: evidence from Australia”
- (94) Melbourne Institute Outlook Conference, Melbourne, October 2018, “The political economy of tax”
- (95) Parliamentary Budget Office, Canberra, September 2018, “An overview of the Australian tax system.”
- (96) Australia-Korea Tax and Welfare Workshop, Seoul, September 2018, “Priorities and challenges for tax reform in Australia”
- (97) Australia-Korea Tax and Welfare Workshop, Seoul, September 2018, “Do earned income tax credits for older workers prolong labor market participation and boost earned income? Evidence from Australia’s Mature Age Worker Tax Offset”
- (98) Commonwealth Department of Jobs and Small Businesses, Canberra, September 2018, “The relationship between immigration to Australia and the labour market outcomes of Australian-born workers”
- (99) Parliamentary Budget Office, Canberra, August 2018, “Do earned income tax credits for older workers prolong labor market participation and boost earned income? Evidence from Australia’s Mature Age Worker Tax Offset”
- (100) Australian Conference of Economists, Canberra, July 2018, “Do earned income tax credits for older workers prolong labour market participation and boost earned income? Evidence from Australia’s Mature Age Worker Tax Offset”
- (101) Australian Conference of Economists, Canberra, July 2018, “Taxpayer responsiveness to marginal tax rates: Bunching evidence from the Australian personal income tax system”
- (102) Public Economics Research Day in New Zealand, April 2018, “Bunching and the elasticity of taxable income: evidence from Australia”
- (103) Monash University, March 2018, “Taxpayer responsiveness to the Australian Taxation System”
- (104) Australasian Agriculture and Resource Economics Society (AARES) 2018 Conference, Adelaide, February 2018, Invited Session: “Perspectives on Agricultural and Applied Economics Journals”
- (105) Asian and Australasian Society of Labour Economics (AASLE), Canberra, December 2017, “As You Sow, So Shall You Reap: The Effect of Article Length on Citation”
- (106) Australian Labour Market Research (ALMR) Workshop, Canberra, December 2017, “Financial stress and equivalence scales: Evidence for Indigenous and non-Indigenous Australians”

- (107) “New approaches to tax and welfare in Australia and Korea”, Canberra, November 2017, “The Elasticity of Taxable Income”
- (108) University of Melbourne, October 2017, “The Elasticity of Taxable Income”
- (109) The Future of the HILDA Survey: Opportunities and Challenges, September 2017, “Maintaining sample representativeness”
- (110) University of Canberra, August 2017, “The Elasticity of Taxable Income”
- (111) Tianjin University of Finance and Economics, June 2017, “Exploring the links between bilateral and regional trade agreements and merchandise trade”
- (112) The Sixth Trade and Development Conference: Global Economic Recovery and Trade Policy Uncertainty, Nankai University, Tianjin, China, June 2017, “Baby Bonuses: Natural Experiments in Cash Transfers, Birth Timing and Child Outcomes”
- (113) Happy Days Workshop, Canberra, December 2016, “Different views of happiness across the social sciences”
- (114) Behavioural Economics Team of the Australian Government (BETA) inaugural academic workshop, Canberra, November 2016, “exploring applications of behavioural economics to key policy challenges”, panellist
- (115) Longitudinal Data Conference 2016, Canberra, October 2016, “Youth mental health and the duration on income support”
- (116) Queensland University of Technology, Brisbane, September 2016, “Is it inequality or poverty that’s bad for growth?”
- (117) 22nd International Panel Data Conference, Perth, June 2016, “Is it inequality or poverty that’s bad for growth?”
- (118) Swinburne University of Technology, Melbourne, March 2016, “Channels of Knowledge Spillover: An Australian Perspective”
- (119) 60th Annual Conference of the Australian Agricultural and Resource Economics Society, AARES2016, Canberra, February 2016, “Natural Disasters and Financial Stress in Agricultural Areas,” special invited session
- (120) Australian Commonwealth Department of Education, Canberra, December 2015, “Empowering women: the role of child care policies”
- (121) Women, Power & Money Symposium, College of Business and Economics, Australian National University, November 2015, “Empowering women: the role of child care policies”
- (122) University of Korea, Seoul, South Korea, November 2015, “The relationship between immigration to Australia and the labour market outcomes of Australian-born workers”
- (123) Industry Summit, Department of Immigration and Border Protection, Melbourne, November 2015. “Understanding the impact of migration on Australian workers”

- (124) University of Wollongong, October 2015, “The relationship between immigration to Australia and the labour market outcomes of Australian-born workers”
- (125) Migrant Intake Inquiry, Productivity Commission, Canberra, October 2015. “Understanding the impact of migration on Australian workers”
- (126) Centre for European Studies, Australian National University, Canberra, August 2015, “Understanding the impact of migration: measures and categories in Europe and Australia”
- (127) Productivity Commission, Canberra, Australia, July 2015, “Knowledge spillovers in Australia”
- (128) University of Canberra, Australia, December 2014, “Demand Uncertainty and Outsourcing”
- (129) Statistical Society of Australia, Canberra, November 2014, “The dynamics of satisfaction with working hours in Australia: the usefulness of panel data in evaluating the case for policy intervention”
- (130) Australian Commonwealth Department of Education, Canberra, August 2014, “Channels of labour supply responses of lone parents to changed work incentives”
- (131) Australian Commonwealth Department of Education, Canberra, March 2014, “Building the evidence to support schooling policy reforms: international perspectives”
- (132) University of Chicago, Chicago, USA, October 2013, “Channels of labour supply responses of lone parents to changed work incentives”
- (133) University of Canterbury, Christchurch, New Zealand, October 2013, “Childcare in Australia”
- (134) Economic Analysis of Industry and Innovation Programs, Canberra, Australia, September, 2013, “Estimation issues in identifying and measuring economic impact”
- (135) University of Queensland, St. Lucia, Australia, August 2013, “Sovereign Ratings and Oil-Producing Countries: Have Sovereign Ratings Run Ahead of Fundamentals?”
- (136) Monash University, Caulfield, Australia, August 2013, “Childcare and Women’s Labour Supply”
- (137) Evidence-based policy making II: Best Practices for Policy Design and Evaluation, Canberra, Australia, July 2013, “Challenges for Evaluation of Social Assistance and Aid Policy”
- (138) Innovation Secretariats Workshop, Canberra, Australia, May 2013, “Innovation and Outsourcing”
- (139) Australian Department of Education, Employment and Workplace Relations, Canberra, Australia, April, 2013, “Child Care Assistance: Are subsidies or tax credits better?”
- (140) Australian Bureau of Statistics, Canberra, Australia, April, 2013, “Using panel data in policy analysis” (Jointly sponsored by the Statistical Society of Australia)

- (141) Australian National University, Canberra, Australia, March, 2013, symposium panelist on “Creating a Productive Future: Social and Economic Challenges, Policy and Governance”
- (142) Université de Rennes I, France, February, 2013, “Childcare in Australia”
- (143) University of Luxembourg, Luxembourg, February, 2013, “Childcare in Australia”
- (144) University of Wisconsin, Madison, Wisconsin, December, 2012, “Childcare in Australia”
- (145) Australian Bureau of Statistics, Canberra, Australia, October, 2012, “The usefulness of panel data: some examples.”
- (146) University of Otago, Dunedin, New Zealand, September, 2012, “The relationship between wage inequality and effort: an application to baseball.”
- (147) Deakin University, Melbourne, Australia, September, 2012, “Childcare in Australia”
- (148) Australian Conference of Economists, Melbourne, Australia, July, 2012, “Immigrant wage assimilation in Australia: the importance of accounting for unobserved heterogeneity.”
- (149) Econometric Society Australasian Meetings, Melbourne, Australia, July, 2012, “Bias correction in panel probit models”
- (150) Econometric Society Australasian Meetings, Melbourne, Australia, July, 2012, “Child care policy: are tax credits or rebates better?”
- (151) Productivity Commission, Canberra, Australia, 5 June, 2012, “Child care subsidies or tax credits: which are better?”
- (152) Indian Statistical Institute, Kolkata, India, February, 2012, “The relationship between wage inequality and effort: an application to baseball.”
- (153) Kolkata University, India, February, 2012, “The relationship between wage inequality and effort: an application to baseball.”
- (154) Jadavpur University, Kolkata, India, February, 2012, “The relationship between wage inequality and effort: an application to baseball.”
- (155) Visva-Bharati University, Santiniketan, India, February, 2012, “Child care in Australia.”
- (156) Centre for Studies in Social Sciences, Calcutta (CSSSC), Kolkata, India, February, 2012, “Child care in Australia.”
- (157) University of Wollongong, Australia, December, 2011, “The relationship between wage inequality and effort: an application to baseball.”
- (158) National Institute for Labour Studies, Flinders University, Adelaide, Australia, November, 2011, “The relationship between wage inequality and effort: an application to baseball.”
- (159) Asian Conference on Applied Micro-Economics/Econometrics, Taipei, Taiwan, November, 2011, “Income pooling between young adults and their parents.”

- (160) University of Tasmania, Hobart, Australia, October, 2011, "Sovereign Ratings and Oil-Producing Countries: Have Sovereign Ratings Run Ahead of Fundamentals?"
- (161) University of Canberra, Australia, August, 2011, "Income pooling between young adults and their parents."
- (162) HILDA Survey Research Conference, Melbourne, Australia, July, 2011, "Mismatch between actual and preferred working hours."
- (163) HILDA Survey Research Conference, Melbourne, Australia, July, 2011, "Estimating net child care price elasticity of partnered women with preschool children using discrete structural labour supply-child care model."
- (164) Australian Conference of Economists, Canberra, Australia, July, 2011, "Estimating net child care price elasticity of partnered women with preschool children using discrete structural labour supply-child care model."
- (165) Australian Conference of Economists, Canberra, Australia, July, 2011, "Child Care Availability, Quality and Affordability: Are Local Problems Related to Labour Supply."
- (166) Australian Conference of Economists, Canberra, Australia, July, 2011, "Partnered Women's Labour Supply and Child Care costs in Australia: Measurement Error and the Child Care Price."
- (167) Econometric Society Australasian Meetings, Adelaide, Australia, July, 2011, "The Effect of Survey Design on Household Reporting of Financial Difficulty."
- (168) Econometric Society Australasian Meetings, Adelaide, Australia, July, 2011, "Exploring the links Between Bilateral and Regional trade Agreements and Merchandise Trade."
- (169) Econometric Society Australasian Meetings, Adelaide, Australia, July, 2011, "Estimating net child care price elasticity of partnered women with preschool children using discrete structural labour supply-child care model."
- (170) Australian Conference of Economists, Sydney, Australia, September, 2010, "Should dynamic demand equations having moving-average components."
- (171) Monash University, September, 2010, "Improved estimates of the responsiveness of married women's labour supply to child care prices."
- (172) Journées de Microéconomie appliquée, Université d'Angers, June, 2010, "Parental and youth mental health and the income support system."
- (173) Paris School of Economics, May, 2010, "Child care availability, quality and affordability: are local problems related to maternal labour supply?"
- (174) OECD, May, 2010 "Child care and maternal labour supply: correcting measurement error using child-level data."
- (175) Université d'Angers, April, 2010, "Child care availability, quality and affordability: are local problems related to maternal labour supply?"

- (176) Colloque francophone sur les sondages, Tangier, Morocco, March, 2010, "The Effect of Survey Design on Household Reporting of Financial Difficulty."
- (177) Université de Rennes I, March, 2010 "Child care and maternal labour supply: correcting measurement error using child-level data."
- (178) Latrobe University, June, 2009, "Child care availability, quality and affordability: are local problems related to maternal labour supply?"
- (179) Public Economics at the Regional Level (PEARL) Conference, Shandong University (China), May, 2009, "Testing regulatory consistency."
- (180) Griffith University, May, 2009, "Improving estimates of petrol price elasticities for Australia and the U.S."
- (181) Macquarie University, April, 2009, "Testing the accuracy of predicted wages for the non-employed."
- (182) Université de Rennes I, January, 2009, "Testing regulatory consistency."
- (183) Public Economic Theory Conference, Seoul, South Korea, July, 2008, "Regulatory consistency in Australia."
- (184) University of Canterbury (New Zealand), August, 2007, "Improved estimates of petrol price elasticities for Australia".
- (185) Econometric Society Australasia Meetings, Brisbane, July, 2007, "Measuring maverick behaviour in the Australian mortgage market."
- (186) Macquarie University, May, 2007, "Understanding the Productivity Performance of Australia in the 1990s".
- (187) Queensland University of Technology, October, 2006, "Understanding the Productivity Performance of Australia in the 1990s".
- (188) University of Adelaide, July, 2006, "Applications of non-parametric econometrics and advances in modeling intra-household economic behaviour."
- (189) Econometric Society Australasia Meetings, Alice Springs, July, 2006, "Club size effect and the provision of local public goods: A semi-parametric analysis using French data."
- (190) CEMFI (Centro de Estudios Monetarios y Financieros)/University Carlos III Madrid, Policy Evaluation Workshop, January, 2006, "A Couple-Based Approach to the Problem of Workless Families."
- (191) University of Girona, January, 2006, "Simple diagnostic testing for Markov-Switching Models with some applications to Spain."
- (192) GATE, Université Lyon II, December, 2005, "Disagreement in Partners' Reports of Material Hardship."
- (193) Université Paris II (Pantheon), November, 2005, "The gender wage gap in France."
- (194) HILDA Survey Research Conference, September, 2005, "Australian Families and the Experience of Financial Difficulty."
- (195) Industry Economics Conference, LaTrobe University, Melbourne, September, 2005, "Price Regulation in Australia: How consistent has it been?"

- (196) Australian Conference of Economists, Melbourne, September, 2005, "Improving the Modeling of Couples' Labour Supply."
- (197) Labour Econometrics Workshop, University of New South Wales, Sydney, August 2005, "Using Financial Difficulty to Estimate Equivalence Scales"
- (198) Australian National University, August 2005, "Congestion effects and municipality size: A non-parametric analysis using French data"
- (199) Hidden Markov Models and Complex Systems, Wanaka, New Zealand, June, 2005, "Simple Methods for Assessing Markov-Switching Models"
- (200) Society for Labor Economics/European Association of Labour Economics World Congress, San Francisco, June, 2005, "Impact of Financial Hardship on Family Labor Supply in Australia".
- (201) Université de Rennes I, February, 2005, "Determinants of firm-level productivity growth: the role of entry and exit."
- (202) University of Wisconsin, Institute for Research on Poverty. Madison, WI, December, 2004, "A new method for estimating equivalence scales using measures of financial hardship."
- (203) Australian Competition and Consumer Commission. Canberra, Australia, November, 2004, "Price Regulation in Australia: How consistent has it been?"
- (204) 2004 Productivity Commission Conference: Quantitative Tools for Microeconomic Policy Analysis, Canberra, Australia, November, 2004, "Estimation of Total Factor Productivity using a new Non-parametric Method that Accounts for Entry and Exit."
- (205) University of Melbourne, Micro-econometrics workshop, Melbourne, October, 2004, "Determinants of firm-level productivity growth: the role of entry and exit."
- (206) Stata Users Group Meeting (Australia), Adelaide, October, 2004, "Australia's firm-level productivity—a new perspective."
- (207) University of Adelaide, October, 2004, "A non-parametric analysis of the male-female wage gap in France."
- (208) Australian Conference of Economists, University of Sydney, September, 2004, "Determinants of firm-level productivity growth: the role of entry and exit."
- (209) Australian Bureau of Statistics, Canberra, September, 2004, "Determinants of firm-level productivity growth: the role of entry and exit."
- (210) Center for Mathematics and its Applications, Australian National University, September, 2004, "Disagreement in Partners' Reports of Material Hardship."
- (211) Econometric Society Australasia Meetings, Monash University, July, 2004, "Disagreement in Partners' Reports of Material Hardship."
- (212) Econometric Society Australasia Meetings, Monash University, July, 2004, "Productivity in Australian Manufacturing: Accounting for Entry and Exit."

- (213) Econometric Society Australasia Meetings, Monash University, July, 2004, "A non-parametric analysis of the male-female wage gap in France."
- (214) Université de Rennes I, February, 2004, "A non-parametric analysis of the male-female wage gap in France."
- (215) Department of Family and Community Services, Social Policy Workshop, November, 2003, "The determinants of financial stress in Australia."
- (216) Conference of Economists (Economic Society of Australia), Australian National University, September, 2003, "The determinants of financial stress in Australia."
- (217) Labour Econometrics Workshop, University of Melbourne, August, 2003, "The female-male wage gap in France: what can be learned from a non-parametric analysis?"
- (218) Econometric Society Australasia Meetings, University of New South Wales, July, 2003, "Understanding the factors associated with financial stress in Australian households."
- (219) Social Policy Research Conference, University of New South Wales, July, 2003, "The determinants of financial stress in Australia."
- (220) Université de Rennes I, February, 2003, "Assisting the long-term unemployed: Results from a randomized trial."
- (221) Public Economic Theory Conference, Paris, July, 2002. "Welfare transfers and intra-household trickle-down: A model with evidence from the US Food Stamp Program."
- (222) International Workshop on Income Distribution and Welfare, Bocconi University Centennial, Milan, Italy, June, 2002, "Bias correction and variance estimation for inequality measures estimated from complex samples."
- (223) EUREQUA, Université Paris I, June, 2002, "Assisting the long-term unemployed: Results from a randomized trial."
- (224) Journées de Microéconomie appliquée, Université de Rennes I, June , 2002, "Assisting the long-term unemployed: Results from a randomized trial."
- (225) U.S. Department of Agriculture, Washington, DC, May, 2002, "Welfare transfers and intra-household trickle-down: A model with evidence from the US Food Stamp Program."
- (226) University of Wisconsin, April, 2002, "Some simple methods for assessing Markov-switching models."
- (227) University of Wisconsin, April, 2002, "Welfare transfers and intra-household trickle-down: A model with evidence from the US Food Stamp Program."
- (228) Australian National University, March, 2002, "Assisting the long-term unemployed: Results from a randomized trial."
- (229) Department of Family and Community Services, December, 2001, "Assisting the long-term unemployed: Results from a randomized trial."

- (230) University of Melbourne, October, 2001. "Some simple methods for assessing Markov-switching models."
- (231) University of Adelaide, August, 2001. "Some simple methods for assessing Markov-switching models."
- (232) Labour Econometrics Workshop, University of New South Wales, August, 2001, "Bias correction and variance estimation for inequality measures estimated from complex samples."
- (233) Econometric Society Australasia Meetings, University of Auckland (New Zealand), July, 2001, "Some simple methods for assessing Markov-switching models."
- (234) University of New South Wales, July, 2001. "Some simple methods for assessing Markov-switching models."
- (235) Australian National University, May, 2001. "Some simple methods for assessing Markov-switching models."
- (236) University of California-Riverside, January, 2001, "Some simple methods for assessing Markov-switching models."
- (237) University of California-Riverside, January, 2000, "A game-theoretic explanation of the cashout puzzle in the US Food Stamp Program."
- (238) University of Sydney, September, 1999, "A game-theoretic explanation of the cashout puzzle in the US Food Stamp Program."
- (239) Statistical Society of Australia, Canberra Branch, August, 1999, "Complex surveys and econometric analysis."
- (240) Econometric Society, Far Eastern Meeting, National University of Singapore, July, 1999, "Complex surveys and econometric analysis."
- (241) Econometric Society Australasia Meetings, University of Sydney, July, 1999, "A game-theoretic explanation of the cashout puzzle in the US Food Stamp Program."
- (242) University of Queensland, May, 1999, "A game-theoretic explanation of the cashout puzzle in the US Food Stamp Program."
- (243) Australian National University, February, 1999, "A game-theoretic explanation of the cashout puzzle in the US Food Stamp Program."
- (244) University of Wisconsin-Milwaukee, October, 1998, "Nonparametric density estimation for stratified samples."
- (245) Deakin University, October, 1998, "Nonparametric density estimation for stratified samples."
- (246) Monash University, October, 1998, "Nonparametric density estimation for stratified samples."
- (247) University of New South Wales, September, 1998, "Nonparametric density estimation for stratified samples."
- (248) University of Sydney Econometrics Workshop, August, 1998, "Nonparametric density estimation for stratified samples."
- (249) Econometric Society Australasia Meetings, Australian National University, July, 1998, "Nonparametric density estimation for stratified samples."

- (250) U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, February, 1998, “Nonparametric density estimation for stratified samples.”
- (251) California State University, Los Angeles, June, 1997, “Complex surveys and econometric analysis.”

- Conference Organizing

- (1) Sixth annual Australian Workshop on Public Finance, Canberra (July 2026)
- (2) Co-chair, program committee, Australian Conference of Economists (ACE), Canberra (July 2026)
- (3) Fifth annual Australian Workshop on Public Finance, Canberra (July-August 2025)
- (4) Australian Academy of Social Sciences Policy Roundtable. Unlocking value: Better use of integrated government data for evidence-based policy (July 2025)
- (5) Fourth annual Australian Workshop on Public Finance, Canberra (June 2024)
- (6) Data Workshop: Good Policy Requires Good Data (June 2024)
- (7) Third annual Australian Workshop on Public Finance, Canberra (July 2023)
- (8) Second annual Australian Workshop on Public Finance, Canberra (August 2022)
- (9) Oceania Stata Conference 2022 (February 2022)
- (10) 2021 A-LIFE Conference and inaugural Australian Workshop on Public Finance, Canberra (March 2021)
- (11) Retirement Income Review Roundtable, Canberra (February 2021)
- (12) What’s new in Behavioural Science?, presented by BEST and TTPI, Canberra (February 2021)
- (13) Tax and Transfer Policy Institute National Covid-19 Tax Summit, Canberra and virtual (August 2020)
- (14) Asian and Australasian Society of Labour Economics (AASLE), Singapore, (December 2019)
- (15) 32nd annual Ph.D. Conference in economics and business, Australian National University, (November 2019)
- (16) Workshop on Data Linkage for Ageing Related Research: How far have we come? How much further to go? Australian National University (April 2019)
- (17) Asian and Australasian Society of Labour Economics (AASLE), Seoul, South Korea, (December 2018)
- (18) Labour Econometrics Workshop, Canberra, Australia, (August, 2016)
- (19) Australian Ph.D. Conference in Business and Economics, Canberra, Australia (November, 2010)

- (20) Econometric Society Australasia Meetings, Canberra, Australia (July, 2009)
- (21) Australian National University Economics Showcase, Canberra, Australia (November, 2008)
- (22) Measurement Error Workshop, Canberra, Australia, (May, 2008)
- (23) Labour Econometrics Workshop, Canberra, Australia, (April, 2008)
- (24) Australian National University Economics Showcase, Canberra, Australia (November, 2007)
- (25) Australia/New Zealand Stata Users Group (SUG) Meeting II, Melbourne, Australia (August, 2006)
- (26) Econometric Society Australasia Meetings, Alice Springs, Australia (July, 2006)
- (27) Econometric Society Asia, Lahore, Pakistan, (December, 2002)
- (28) Labour Econometrics Workshop, Canberra, Australia, (August, 2002)

- Other Conference Participation

- (1) Economic Reform Roundtable hosted by Treasurer Jim Chalmers, invited speaker. Parliament House, Canberra, Australia (August 2025)
- (2) Roundtable on Contributing to Productivity, Resilience and Budget Sustainability Through Workforce Participation: Moving from Welfare to Work, hosted by Social Services Minister Tanya Plibersek, invited speaker. Parliament House, Canberra, Australia (August 2025)
- (3) Labour Econometrics Workshop, University of Melbourne (August, 2025), discussant.
- (4) Workforce Participation: Moving from Welfare to Work Roundtable, Parliament House, invited speaker. Canberra, Australia (12 August 2025).
- (5) Academics and Think Tanks Productivity Roundtable, invited speaker. Melbourne, Australia (7 August 2025)
- (6) Allegra Spender's Tax Reform Roundtable at Parliament House, invited participant. Canberra, Australia (July 2025)
- (7) Amplify Citizen's Forum. Sydney, Australia (February 2025), invited presenter.
- (8) Roundtable for Institutional Change to Better Promote Present and Future Well-Being, invited participant. Australian National University, Canberra, Australia (September 2024)
- (9) Reserve Bank of Australia Conference on Human Capital, Sydney (June 2024), invited participant.
- (10) Reserve Bank of Australia Economic Implications of the Digital Economy Conference, Sydney (March 2022), invited participant.
- (11) Reserve Bank of Australia policy conference, Sydney (April 2020), invited participant.
- (12) Global Forum on Productivity, Sydney, Australia (June 2019), invited participant.
- (13) Reserve Bank of Australia low wage conference, Sydney (April 2019), invited participant.
- (14) Labour Econometrics Workshop, University of Sydney (August, 2018), discussant.
- (15) Ph.D. Conference in economics and business, University of New South Wales (October, 2018), discussant.
- (16) Gender and Labour Markets in Asia, Australian National University (September, 2017), chair.
- (17) Labour Econometrics Workshop, University of Auckland (August, 2017), discussant.
- (18) Australian Labour Market Research workshop, Canberra, Australia (December, 2016), discussant
- (19) Colloque L'Indépendance des Universités, Université de la Nouvelle-Calédonie, Noumea (November 2016), invited contributor

- (20) Public Policy Dean's Forum, Shanghai Jiao Tong University, Shanghai, China (May 2016), invited contributor
- (21) Global Public Policy Network (GPPN), São Paulo, Brazil (November, 2015), invited participant.
- (22) Australian Federal Policy Future Directions Project, Canberra Roundtable, Canberra, Australia (October, 2015), invited participant.
- (23) Labour Econometrics Workshop, University of New South Wales (August, 2015), discussant.
- (24) Ph.D. Conference in economics and business, Monash University (November, 2014), discussant.
- (25) Immigration Workshop, University of Melbourne, Melbourne, Australia (July, 2013), discussant.
- (26) Improving collaboration between the APS and researchers, Canberra, Australia (June, 2013) invited participant.
- (27) HC Coombs Policy Forum. FUTURE PERSPECTIVES: Joint HC Coombs Policy Forum, DISSRTE and APSC initiative, Canberra, Australia (March, 2013) invited participant.
- (28) HC Coombs Policy Forum. Indigenous data: A scoping workshop on enhanced access and creative use of data on Indigenous Australians, Canberra, Australia (April, 2011) invited discussant.
- (29) Social Science Perspectives on the 2008 National Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Social Survey, Canberra, Australia (April, 2011) invited discussant.
- (30) Competition, Innovation and Productivity, Canberra, Australia (June, 2009), invited discussant.
- (31) Productivity Perspectives, Canberra, Australia (December, 2007), invited panelist.
- (32) Labour Econometrics Workshop, Wellington, New Zealand (August, 2007), discussant.
- (33) An International Perspective on Immigration and Immigration Policy, Australian National University (December, 2006), discussant.
- (34) Ph.D. Conference in economics and business, Australian National University (November, 2006), discussant.
- (35) Labour Econometrics Workshop, University of Adelaide (August, 2006), discussant and enthusiastic participant in post-conference wine tour.
- (36) Roads to Riches: Economic Growth, Productivity and Development in 2005 Conference, Australian National University (November, 2005), discussant.
- (37) Ph.D. Conference in economics and business, Australian National University (October, 2004), discussant.
- (38) Poverty, Inequality, Labour Market and Welfare Reform in China, Canberra, Australia (August, 2004), discussant for "The impact of institutions, information and demographics on the re-employment of China's laid-off workers," by F. Cai, J. Giles, and A. Park.

- (39) Labour Econometrics Workshop, Auckland, New Zealand (August, 2004), discussant for “A comparison of consistent nonparametric tests for Lorenz dominance,” by G. Barrett, D. Bhattacharya, and S. Donald.
- (40) Australian Health Economics Society Conference, Canberra, Australia (October, 2003), discussant for “Medical expenditures and health status in Australia: A story of increasing or decreasing returns?” by L. Connelly and D. Doessel.
- (41) Ph.D. Conference in economics and business, Australian National University (October, 2002), discussant.
- (42) Australian Labour Market Research Conference, University of Canberra (December, 2001), discussant.
- (43) Ph.D. Conference in economics and business, Australian National University (September, 2000), discussant for “Determinants of Household Food Security in Rural Uganda: An Application of a non-separable Agricultural household model ” by S. Ssewanyana.
- (44) Labour Econometrics Workshop, Hobart, Tasmania (April, 2000), discussant for “Interpreting models with multiple dummy variables,” by J. Hirschberg and J. Lye.
- (45) Department of Family and Community Services, Social Policy Workshop, (March, 2000), discussant for “Participation and claimant status of persons on more than minimum family payment” by D. Johnson, M. Harris, and R. Scutella.

- Other Professional Activity

- Member, judging panel for the 2026 APS Data Awards
- Editorial Board, *Journal of Quantitative Economics*
- Editorial Board, *Australian Journal of Labour Economics*
- Book Review Editor, *Economic Record*
- Judge for best student paper at Economic Society Australia Meetings, July 2017.
- Policy Advising and Skill-building for Government Agencies
I regularly provide advice on the design and conduct of research for a wide range of government agencies. I review internal research and engage in research collaboration. I provide specialized training in econometrics and statistics. Partnerships include:
 - * Commonwealth Department of Treasury, Australia
 - * Commonwealth Department of Prime Minister and Cabinet, Australia
 - * Commonwealth Department of Employment, Australia
 - * Commonwealth Department of Education, Australia
 - * Commonwealth Department of Communication and the Arts, Australia

- * Commonwealth Department of Social Services; Australia
 - * Commonwealth Department of Employment and Workplace Relations, Australia
 - * Productivity Commission, Australia
 - * Australian Taxation Office
 - * U.S. Department of Agriculture
 - * Commonwealth Department of Families, Housing, Community Services and Indigenous Affairs, Australia
 - * Ministry of Business, Innovation and Employment, New Zealand
 - * Fair Work Australia
 - * Australian Bureau of Statistics
 - * Commonwealth Department of Industry, Innovation, Climate Change, Science, Research and Tertiary Education
 - * Equal Opportunity for Women in the Workplace Agency
 - * Ministry of Finance, Sri Lanka
 - * Victorian Treasury
- Book reviews
- Ugo Gentilini's Timely Cash: Lessons from 2500 years of giving people money in *Economic Record*, forthcoming.
- Andrew Leigh's Fair Game: Lessons from Sport for a Fairer Society & a Stronger Economy in *Economic Record*, Volume 99, Number 326, pp 454 - 455, September, 2023.
- Lawrence Tabak's Foxconned: Imaginary jobs, bulldozed homes & the sacking of local government in *Economic Record*, Volume 98, Number 323, pp 408 - 410, December, 2022.
- Werner Troesken's The Pox of Liberty: How the Constitution Left Americans Rich, Free and Prone to Infection in *Economic Record*, Volume 98, Number 322, pp 318 - 319, September, 2022.
- Richard Pomfret's The Economic Integration of Europe in *Economic Record*, Volume 98, Number 321, pp 230 - 231, June, 2022.
- G. M. Hodgson's Wrong Turnings: How the Left Got Lost in *Economic Record*, Volume 98, Number 320, pp 113 - 115, March, 2022.
- Paul Frijters, Gigi Foster and Michael Baker's The Great Covid Panic: What Happened, Why and What to do next in *Economic Record*, Volume 97, Number 319, pp 564 - 565, December, 2021.
- K. Reinert's An Introduction to International Economics: New Perspectives on the World Economy in *Economic Record*, Volume 97, Number 318, pp 440 - 441, September, 2021.
- Joshua Gans and Andrew Leigh's Innovation + Inequality: How to create a future that is more Star Trek than Terminator in *Economic Record*, Volume 97, Number 316, pp 125 - 126, March, 2021.
- A. Goldstein's Janesville: An American Story in *Economic Record*, Volume 95, Number 308, pp 161 - 163, March, 2019.
- W. Baumol's The Cost Disease: Why Computers Get Cheaper and Health Care Doesn't in *Economic Record*, Volume 90, Number 290, pp 414-415, September, 2014.
- A. Ullah and D. Giles, editors Handbook of Empirical Economics and Finance

- in *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, Volume 108, Number 501, pp. 355-6, March, 2013.
- I. Ahamada and E. Flachaire's Non-parametric Econometrics in *Economic Record*, Volume 87, Number 278, pp 494-496, September, 2011.
- Q. Li and J. S. Racine's Nonparametric Econometrics in *Economic Record*, Volume 87, Number 278, pp 494-496, September, 2011.
- P. Cahuc and A. Zylberberg's The Natural Survival of Work: Job Creation and Job Destruction in a Growing Economy in *Economic Record*, Volume 86, Number 275, pp 638-640, December, 2010.
- J. Nelson's Economics for Humans in *Economic Record*, Volume 86, Number 273, pp 303-304, June, 2010.
- P. Le Gall's A History of Econometrics in France: From Nature to Models in *Economic Record*, Volume 85, Number 269, pp. 224-226, June, 2009.
- R. Davidson and J. MacKinnon's Econometric Theory and Methods in *Economic Record*, Volume 83, Number 260, pp. 110-112, March, 2007.
- J. Hamilton's Econometric Theory in *Economic Record*, Volume 77, Number 238, pp. 310-312, September, 2001.

- Other professional service
 - Strategic Examination of Research & Development, Department of Industry (2025)
 - Australian Statistics Advisory Council, Australian Bureau of Statistics (July 2022 - present)
 - Interim Economic Inclusion Advisory Committee (December 2022 - present)
 - Advisory Board Member, National Seniors Australia (December 2022 - present)
 - Advisory Board Member, Behavioural Economics, Society and Technology (BEST) Centre, Queensland University of Technology (April 2022 - present)
 - Australian Institute for Police Management Global Professoriate (January 2020 - present)
 - Member, Economic Society of Australia (ESA) National Economic Panel
 - Australian Capital Territory (ACT) Government Tax Reform Advisory Group
 - Critical Friends of the Central Analytics Hub (July 2018 - present)
 - Parliamentary Budget Office, Panel of Expert Advisors (January 2018 - present)
 - Data Methods Advisory Group, Commonwealth Department of Health (April 2017 - present)
 - Australian Longitudinal Census Dataset Advisory Group (2016 - present)
 - University of Queensland, Honours thesis moderation, (November 2015)
 - Australian Bureau of Statistics Methodology Advisory Committee (MAC) (2008 - 2022)
 - Technical Reference Group, Living in Australia (HILDA) Survey (2006 - present)
 - Productivity Measurement Reference Group, Australian Bureau of Statistics (2005 - present)
 - Labour Statistics Advisory Group, Australian Bureau of Statistics (2002 - present)
 - Member, academic advisory board, Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) project on Tax and Economic Growth (2007)
- Special courses
 - * “Getting started: Analyzing HILDA with STATA.” Melbourne Institute of Applied Economic and Social Research, Melbourne, November 2025.
 - * “The Economics of Industry and Innovation Policy.” Course delivered for the Australian Treasury, June 2025.
 - * “Getting started: Analyzing HILDA with STATA.” Melbourne Institute of Applied Economic and Social Research, Canberra, June 2025.
 - * “Introduction to Panel Data Analysis.” Melbourne Institute of Applied Economic and Social Research, Canberra, June 2025.

- * “Economics of Tax Policy.” Course delivered for the Australian Treasury, June 2025.
- * “Econometrics and Evaluation Methods.” Course delivered for the Commonwealth Department of Education, March 2025.
- * “Economics of Tax Policy.” Course delivered for the Australian Treasury, February 2025.
- * “Economics of Tax Policy.” Course delivered for the Australian Treasury, November 2024.
- * “Getting started: Analyzing HILDA with STATA.” Melbourne Institute of Applied Economic and Social Research, Melbourne, September 2024.
- * “Introduction to Panel Data Analysis.” Melbourne Institute of Applied Economic and Social Research, Melbourne, May 2024.
- * “Getting started: Analyzing HILDA with STATA.” Melbourne Institute of Applied Economic and Social Research, Canberra, April 2024.
- * “Getting started: Analyzing HILDA with STATA.” Melbourne Institute of Applied Economic and Social Research, Melbourne, October 2023.
- * “Getting started: Analyzing HILDA with STATA.” Victorian Department of Treasury and Finance, Melbourne, May 2023.
- * “Getting started: Analyzing HILDA with STATA.” Melbourne Institute of Applied Economic and Social Research, Canberra, February 2023.
- * “Introduction to Panel Data Analysis.” With the Melbourne Institute of Applied Economic and Social Research, Canberra, February 2023.
- * “Getting started: Analyzing HILDA with STATA.” Australian Institute for Health and Welfare, Canberra, October 2022.
- * “Getting started: Analyzing HILDA with STATA.” Melbourne Institute of Applied Economic and Social Research, Melbourne, June 2022.
- * “Introduction to Panel Data Analysis.” With the Melbourne Institute of Applied Economic and Social Research, Melbourne, June 2022.
- * “Getting started: Analyzing HILDA with STATA.” Melbourne Institute of Applied Economic and Social Research, Melbourne, June 2021.
- * “Introduction to Panel Data Analysis.” With the Melbourne Institute of Applied Economic and Social Research, Melbourne, June 2021.
- * “Economics of Tax Policy.” Course delivered for the Commonwealth Department of Prime Minister and Cabinet. February 2020.
- * “Introduction to Panel Data Analysis.” With the Melbourne Institute of Applied Economic and Social Research, Canberra, February 2020.

- * “Getting started: Analyzing HILDA with STATA.” Melbourne Institute of Applied Economic and Social Research, Canberra, February 2020.
- * “Economics for Policy Makers.” Course delivered for the Commonwealth Department of Prime Minister and Cabinet. January - February 2020.
- * “A Beginner’s Guide to Economics” Course delivered for the Commonwealth Department of Communication and the Arts. November 2019.
- * “Economics of Tax Policy.” Course delivered for the Australian Treasury. November 2019.
- * “Economic Literacy for Non-Economists.” Course delivered for the Commonwealth Department of Foreign Affairs and Trade. Three courses. September - October 2019.
- * “Beginner’s guide to microeconomics for the public sector.” Crawford School of Public Policy Executive Education, September, 2019.
- * “Beginner’s guide to macroeconomics for the public sector.” Crawford School of Public Policy Executive Education, September, 2019.
- * “Introduction to Economics for Policy Makers.” Course delivered for the Social Policy Division of the Commonwealth Department of Prime Minister and Cabinet. August 2019.
- * “Introduction to Economics for Policy Makers.” Course delivered for the Australian Treasury. June 2019.
- * “Using STATA for panel data analysis.” Course delivered as part of the Oceania STATA Conference, Parramatta, Australia. August 2019.
- * “Introduction to Economics.” Course delivered for the Commonwealth Department of Prime Minister and Cabinet. June 2019.
- * “Economics of Tax Policy.” Course delivered for the Australian Treasury. June 2019.
- * “Essentials of Economic Thinking and Economic Development.” Course delivered for the Regional Network, Indigenous Affairs Group of the Commonwealth Department of Prime Minister and Cabinet. April - May 2019.
- * “Getting started: Analyzing HILDA with STATA.” Melbourne Institute of Applied Economic and Social Research, Canberra, April 2019.
- * “Introduction to Economics.” Course delivered for the Commonwealth Department of Prime Minister and Cabinet. April 2019.
- * “The Economics of Tax Policy.” Crawford School of Public Policy Executive Education, March 2019.
- * “Economic Literacy for Non-Economists.” Course delivered for the Commonwealth Department of Foreign Affairs and Trade. Four courses. October - November 2018.

- * “Economic Literacy for Non-Economists.” Course delivered for the Office for Women in Department of Prime Minister and Cabinet. December 2018.
- * “Introduction to Economics.” Course delivered for the Commonwealth Department of Prime Minister and Cabinet. October 2018.
- * “Introduction to Panel Data Analysis.” with the Melbourne Institute of Applied Economic and Social Research, Melbourne, September 2018.
- * “Beginner’s guide to microeconomics for the public sector.” Special course for the Department of Industry, September, 2018.
- * “Beginner’s guide to macroeconomics for the public sector.” Special course for the Department of Industry, August, 2018.
- * “Getting started: Analyzing HILDA with STATA.” Melbourne Institute of Applied Economic and Social Research, September 2018.
- * “Getting started: Analyzing HILDA with R.” Australian Treasury, August 2018.
- * “Beginner’s guide to microeconomics for the public sector.” Crawford School of Public Policy Executive Education, July, 2018.
- * “Beginner’s guide to macroeconomics for the public sector.” Crawford School of Public Policy Executive Education, July, 2018.
- * “Economic Growth.” Crawford School of Public Policy Executive Education, June, 2018.
- * “Getting started: Analyzing HILDA with STATA.” Melbourne Institute of Applied Economic and Social Research, June 2018.
- * “Introduction to Economics.” Course delivered for the Commonwealth Department of Prime Minister and Cabinet. May 2018.
- * “A Beginner’s Guide to Economics” Course delivered for the Commonwealth Department of Communication and the Arts. March 2018.
- * “Introduction to Panel Data Analysis.” with the Melbourne Institute of Applied Economic and Social Research, Canberra, February 2018.
- * “Understanding the Economics of Tax Policy.” Course delivered for the Australian Taxation Office, November 2017.
- * “Introduction to Economics.” Course delivered for the Commonwealth Department of Prime Minister and Cabinet. October 2017 - November 2017.
- * “Economic Literacy for Non-Economists.” Course delivered for the Commonwealth Department of Foreign Affairs and Trade. Six courses. October 2017 - April 2018.
- * “Getting started: Analyzing HILDA with STATA.” with the Melbourne Institute of Applied Economic and Social Research, Melbourne, September 2017.
- * “Introduction to economics for the public service.” Tailored course for Commonwealth Department of Education. Crawford School of Public Policy. June, 2017.

- * “Economic Growth.” Crawford School of Public Policy Executive Education, May, 2017.
- * “Beginner’s guide to microeconomics for the public sector.” Crawford School of Public Policy Executive Education, May, 2017.
- * “Beginner’s guide to macroeconomics for the public sector.” Crawford School of Public Policy Executive Education, May, 2017.
- * “Getting started: Analyzing HILDA with STATA.” with the Melbourne Institute of Applied Economic and Social Research, Canberra, February 2017.
- * “Beginner’s guide to microeconomics for the public sector.” Crawford School of Public Policy Executive Education, November, 2016.
- * “Beginner’s guide to macroeconomics for the public sector.” Crawford School of Public Policy Executive Education, November, 2016.
- * “Getting started: Analyzing HILDA with STATA.” Melbourne Institute of Applied Economic and Social Research, September 2016.
- * “Macroeconomics: Basic tools, concepts and insights & understanding open-economy and interpreting trade statistics” Department of Foreign Affairs and Trade (through Crawford School of Public Policy Executive Education Program), September, 2016. (two courses)
- * “Basic Microeconomics and Australia’s Microeconomic Reform Challenges” Department of Foreign Affairs and Trade (through Crawford School of Public Policy Executive Education Program), September, 2016. (two courses)
- * “Panel data basics.” Australian Bureau of Statistics, June, 2016.
- * “Beginner’s guide to microeconomics for the public sector.” Crawford School of Public Policy Executive Education, May, 2016.
- * “Beginner’s guide to macroeconomics for the public sector.” Crawford School of Public Policy Executive Education, May, 2016.
- * “A Beginner’s Guide to Economics” Department of Communication and the Arts (through Crawford School of Public Policy Executive Education Program), May, 2015.
- * “Beginner’s guide to microeconomics for the public sector.” Crawford School of Public Policy Executive Education, November, 2015.
- * “Beginner’s guide to macroeconomics for the public sector.” Crawford School of Public Policy Executive Education, November, 2015.
- * “Economics of Tax Policy.” Crawford School of Public Policy Executive Education, October, 2015.
- * “Basic Microeconomics and Australia’s Microeconomic Reform Challenges” Department of Foreign Affairs and Trade (through Crawford School of Public Policy Executive Education Program), September, 2015. (two courses)

- * “Economics of Tax Policy.” Australian Taxation Office, August 2015.
- * “Getting started: Analyzing HILDA with STATA.” Melbourne Institute of Applied Economic and Social Research, June 2015.
- * “Beginner’s guide to microeconomics for the public sector.” Crawford School of Public Policy Executive Education, May, 2015.
- * “Beginner’s guide to macroeconomics for the public sector.” Crawford School of Public Policy Executive Education, May, 2015.
- * “A Beginner’s Guide to Economics” Department of Communication (through Crawford School of Public Policy Executive Education Program), March, 2015.
- * “Getting started: Analyzing HILDA with STATA.” Melbourne Institute of Applied Economic and Social Research, February 2015.
- * “Applied Longitudinal Data Analysis.” Australian Consortium for Social and Political Research Incorporated, February 2015.
- * “Introduction to Statistics and Econometrics” Department of Communication (through Crawford School of Public Policy Executive Education Program), January 2015.
- * “A Beginner’s Guide to Economics” Department of Communication (through Crawford School of Public Policy Executive Education Program), November/December, 2014.
- * “Beginner’s guide to microeconomics for the public sector.” Crawford School of Public Policy Executive Education, October, 2014.
- * “Beginner’s guide to macroeconomics for the public sector.” Crawford School of Public Policy Executive Education, October, 2014.
- * “Getting started: basic data analysis for policy” Commonwealth Department of Education, May, 2014.
- * “Basic Microeconomics and Australia’s Microeconomic Reform Challenges” Department of Foreign Affairs and Trade (through Crawford School of Public Policy Executive Education Program), August/September, 2014. (two courses)
- * “Using STATA for evaluation” Commonwealth Department of Employment, May, 2014.
- * “Getting started: Analyzing HILDA with STATA.” Melbourne Institute of Applied Economic and Social Research (conducted at Australian National University), April 2014.
- * “Beginner’s guide to microeconomics for the public sector.” Crawford School of Public Policy Executive Education, April, 2014.
- * “Beginner’s guide to macroeconomics for the public sector.” Crawford School of Public Policy Executive Education, April, 2014.
- * “Evaluation.” Commonwealth Department of Employment, November, 2013.
- * “Introductory Micro-economics.” Australian National Institute for Public Policy, November, 2013.
- * “Introductory Macro-economics.” Australian National Institute for Public Policy, November, 2013.

- * “Interpreting and Understanding the Significance and Limitations of Economic Data and Statistics.” Department of Foreign Affairs and Trade (through Crawford School of Public Policy Executive Education Program), September, 2013.
- * “Getting started: Analyzing HILDA with STATA.” Melbourne Institute of Applied Economic and Social Research, October, 2013.
- * “Econometrics: tricks, traps and ideas.” Commonwealth Department of the Treasury, May - June, 2013.
- * “Getting started: Analyzing HILDA with STATA.” Melbourne Institute of Applied Economic and Social Research (conducted at University of New South Wales), April, 2013.
- * “Interpreting and Understanding the Significance and Limitations of Economic Data and Statistics.” Department of Foreign Affairs and Trade (through Crawford School of Public Policy Executive Education Program), April, 2013.
- * “Getting started: Analyzing HILDA with STATA.” Melbourne Institute of Applied Economic and Social Research (conducted at Australian National University), September 2012.
- * “Using HILDA: Getting going with the data and analyzing the results.” Commonwealth Department of the Treasury, May - June, 2012.
- * “Getting started with HILDA.” Melbourne Institute of Applied Economic and Social Research (conducted at Australian National University), April 2012.
- * “Panel Data Analysis.” Commonwealth Department of the Treasury, April - June, 2011.
- * “Limited Dependent Variables.” Commonwealth Department of the Treasury, September, 2010.
- * “Limited Dependent Variables.” Commonwealth Department of the Treasury, May-October, 2008.
- * “Panel Data Econometrics.” University of Western Sydney, December 3-5, 2007.
- * “Panel Data Econometrics.” Reserve Bank of Australia, October 11-12, 2007.
- * “Vector Auto-Regressions.” Commonwealth Department of the Treasury, August-September, 2007.
- * “Introductory Time Series Econometrics.” Commonwealth Department of the Treasury, March-July, 2007.
- * “Panel Data Econometrics.” Sydney University, February 7-9, 2007.
- * “Econometrics and Evaluation Methods.” Commonwealth Department of Employment and Workplace Relations, December, 2006-February, 2007.
- * “Limited Dependent Variables.” Commonwealth Department of the Treasury, August-September, 2006.
- * “Panel Data Econometrics.” Melbourne Institute for Applied Economic Research, August 7-9, 2006.

- * “Introductory Time Series Econometrics.” Commonwealth Department of the Treasury, March-July, 2006.
 - * “Beginning Gauss Programming.” Commonwealth Department of Family and Community Services, May 30-June 8, 2006.
 - * “Limited Dependent Variables.” Commonwealth Department of Industry, Tourism and Resources, May 17-25, 2006.
 - * “Regulatory Econometrics.” Australian Centre for Regulatory Economics (ACORE), September 5-9, 2005.
 - * “Beginning Gauss Programming.” Commonwealth Department of the Treasury, August 24-31, 2005.
 - * “Panel Data Econometrics.” Macquarie University, July 27-29, 2005.
 - * “Panel Data Econometrics.” University of Western Sydney, March 19 and 26, 2004.
 - * “Panel Data Econometrics.” Department of Family and Community Services, February 23-25, 2004.
 - * “Going beyond the basics: advanced econometric methods.” Productivity Commission. October 31-November 6, 2002.
 - * “Panel Data Econometrics.” Department of Family and Community Services, September 26-28, 2001.
- Judge for best student paper at Econometric Society Australasia Meetings, July 2003.
- External Ph.D. Examination
- * “Productivity decomposition, price imputation and firm dynamics” by Shipei Zeng, University of New South Wales, June 2021
 - * “Essays on Policy Evaluation in Australia” by James Bishop, The University of Sydney, January 2021
 - * “Voters and Politicians: three papers in applied political-economics” by Eamon McGinn, University of Technology Sydney, December 2020
 - * “Essays on Economics of Immigration into Australia” by Toan Truong Nguyen, Curtin University, December 2019.
 - * “The Effect of Trade Liberalisation on Wages: Evidence from China” by Qiong Huang, University of New South Wales, April 2015.
 - * “Four essays on modelling and estimating consumer heterogeneity in probabilistic choice and household demand systems” by Hong Yoo, University of New South Wales, November 2012.
 - * “Three Essays on Monetary Policy Analysis in Mongolia” by Davaaajargal Luvsannyam, Australian National University, September 2012.
 - * “Essays on portfolio allocation and wealth: evidence in Australia” by Elisabeth Kim Anh-Thu Huynh, University of Sydney, December 2010.
 - * “Competition in a spatial retail petroleum market” by N. Wills-Johnson, Curtin University of Technology, March 2010.

- * “Returns to Scale, Technical Progress and Firm Dynamics in Australia” by T.V. Nguyen, University of New South Wales, November, 2009.
- * “Essays on economic growth, structural reform and trade in transitional economies” by R. Hasanova, Asia Pacific School of Economics and Government, Australian National University, April, 2006.
- * “The Impact of Market Reform, Monetary Policy and Financial Aid on Economics Development, with Application to Tajikistan” by M. Tashrifov. Asia Pacific School of Economics and Government, Australian National University, July 2005.
- * “Significance editing and artificial neural networks” by J. Chipperfield. Statistics Department, Australian National University, July 2002.
- * “Some Contributions to systematic sampling schemes” by N. Uthayakumaran. Statistics Department, University of Madras, Chennai, India. July, 1999.